

Foundational Cyberinfrastructure for Open Plasma Science¹

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Project Summary

Overview

PlasmaPy is an open source Python package containing core functionality for plasma science. The overall mission of the PlasmaPy project is to grow a fully open source software ecosystem for plasma research and education: a collection of scientific software packages that are developed together, work together, and co-evolve in the same environment. The project team will expand PlasmaPy to include additional, powerful tools for analyzing data from the most important and widely used diagnostics in high energy density physics and magnetized laboratory plasma experiments. The team will expand functionality needed by the heliophysics community to analyze and understand measurements of plasma in the solar wind, Earth's magnetosphere, and coronal mass ejections. They will then develop software infrastructure in PlasmaPy to make laboratory plasma data sets findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) and improve the plasma science data environment. The proposed enhancements to PlasmaPy are focused on three scientific areas (laboratory plasma physics, high energy density physics, and heliophysics) and will be developed in close collaboration with researchers in these communities. Because few members of the plasma community are experienced contributors to open source software projects, the project team will forge a partnership between PlasmaPy and the Computational Research Access Network (CRANE) and provide numerous training opportunities for undergraduate and post-baccalaureate students and plasma scientists. These opportunities are needed to train the next generation of research software engineers (RSEs) in plasma science and significantly grow the contributor base for PlasmaPy.

Intellectual Merit

This project team will enhance PlasmaPy with functionality for the most important diagnostics in both magnetized laboratory plasma experiments and high energy density physics. This functionality will facilitate innovation by enabling researchers to interpret diagnostic data sets and investigate fundamental science questions related to plasma turbulence, magnetic reconnection, collisionless shocks, wave interactions, coronal heating, instabilities, and particle acceleration. By providing the plasma community with reliable and interoperable open source software, this project will lay a foundation for transparent and

¹ This collaborative research proposal was submitted to the Framework Implementations track of the Cyberinfrastructure for Sustained Scientific Innovation (CSSI) program of the National Science Foundation on December 1, 2025.

reproducible plasma science. This project will lessen the time needed and difficulty experienced by researchers to achieve scientific understanding and innovation by making it easier to compare results from different experiments, perform cross-facility and cross-disciplinary studies, and develop new experimental facilities. By improving PlasmaPy interoperability in the Python ecosystem for heliophysics, this project will reduce the effort needed by scientists to analyze space plasma data. Enhancements to the PlasmaPy software ecosystem will be made in close collaborations with MagNetUS, the Python in Heliophysics Community, and members of the high energy density physics community. Improvements to the plasma science data environment are needed to perform artificial intelligence and machine learning studies in plasma science that use data from more than one experiment.

Broader Impacts

This project will grow and sustain the next generation of RSEs and computational physicists in plasma science via frequent research software engineering tutorials, multiple year-long training opportunities, and through supporting five CRANE online course cycles for undergraduate students in computational physics. Growing the PlasmaPy ecosystem allows the plasma community to pool resources and reduce the cost required for building new plasma experiments, especially at small institutions. This project will broaden access to plasma science for all Americans by providing free access to well-documented and well-tested software. As a free tool, PlasmaPy can facilitate economic development through use at fusion energy startups and small businesses that focus on plasma diagnostics and other plasma technology. The project team will continue to enhance PlasmaPy's documentation and promote it as a freely available educational resource for plasma science, including notebooks that use PlasmaPy to introduce plasma physics concepts. This effort will provide functionality that is beneficial for a wide variety of fields, including laboratory plasma physics, high energy density physics, solar physics, space plasma physics, astrophysics, low temperature plasma, and fusion energy sciences.

Project Description

1. Introduction

Software drives innovation in all areas of plasma science and engineering. Purposeful software allows plasma physicists to design, envision, and understand the field in new ways. Laboratory plasma physicists utilize software when calibrating plasma diagnostics and analyzing experimental data. Space scientists use software to interpret *in situ* observations of space plasma. Computational plasma scientists use software to simulate the behavior of laboratory, heliospheric, and astrophysical plasmas. Fusion energy scientists use software to model plasma behavior, predict stability, and improve confinement. Theoreticians use software to derive models and visualize results. Educators and students use software to interactively explore plasma phenomena and share understanding of plasma concepts.

Plasma science has historically lacked a culture where software was openly developed and shared as a community. Research groups have typically developed analysis codes in-house as needed, so there has been little emphasis on interoperability. Plasma code development has primarily focused on getting results to put in research publications, which makes the resulting code harder to reuse or repurpose for different applications. Submitting journal articles has generally been prioritized over writing documentation and improving user experience. Codes have often lacked a testing framework, which can make users reluctant to make changes for fear of breaking something somewhere else in the code. These factors have limited scientific innovation and increased the difficulty of starting research, reproducing scientific results, and collaborating within or across disciplines.

PlasmaPy began in 2017 as a grassroots effort by students and scientists who were motivated to fundamentally change how the plasma community develops software. Following inspiration from the Astropy and SunPy communities (Astropy Collaboration 2022; SunPy Community 2023), we invited the community to create a Python package for plasma physics. After making two development releases, we received a five-year collaborative NSF CSSI Framework award in 2019 that enabled us to transform PlasmaPy into a mature, well-established package with 150 contributors. We propose a sequel to this award. The first award created the foundation for PlasmaPy and firmly established its presence in the community. This second award will focus on long-term sustainability by broadening the pool of core contributors, training early career plasma scientists in research software engineering, and increasing interoperability among existing software packages. Due to the interdisciplinary nature of plasma science,¹ **PlasmaPy is now used in heliophysics, high energy density physics (HEDP), laboratory plasma physics, astrophysics, low temperature plasma science, and fusion energy sciences.** The need for PlasmaPy has been recognized in high-level community reports for plasma science,² fusion energy sciences,^{3,4} and HEDP.⁵

The mission of the PlasmaPy project is to grow a fully open source software ecosystem for plasma research and education. A software ecosystem is a collection of interoperable software packages that are developed and co-evolve in the same environment. A software ecosystem includes

¹ This proposal is most relevant to the MPS/PHY, GEO/AGS, and MPS/AST divisions of NSF.

² The Plasma 2020 decadal review (NASEM 2021) recommends: “Funding agencies, and in particular DOE and NSF, should support mechanisms for making computational plasma software more widely accessible to noncomputing experts, and to transition current codes to new computing architectures.”

³ The final report of the American Physical Society (APS) Division of Plasma Physics (DPP) Community Planning Process includes community consensus recommendations to: “Establish a network program to foster the development of an open source, programming ecosystem for plasma physics and advance computational plasma science” and “Support improvements to the accessibility, interoperability, reproducibility, and user-friendliness of FES-funded codes and their outputs” (APS DPP CPP 2020).

⁴ FESAC (2020) recommends to “Support networks to coordinate research and broaden access to state-of-the-art facilities, diagnostics, and computational tools.”

⁵ LaserNetUS (2023) states that “Common analysis codes should be open source and written for easy sharing throughout the community” and “Repeatable, open-source-analysis routines could be adapted into an existing code base, such as PlasmaPy.”

code, documentation, tests, educational resources, and community. PlasmaPy itself contains functionality that is broadly needed by plasma scientists across subdisciplines. The PlasmaPy ecosystem includes established packages like `fiasco` for providing access to atomic data (Barnes et al. 2024) and `bapsflib` (Everson et al. 2024) for providing access to data from the Basic Plasma Science Facility (BaPSF), and newer packages like `WiPPLPy` (for the Wisconsin Plasma Physics Laboratory; WiPPL) and `pygasus3` (for the Pegasus III tokamak at the University of Wisconsin). As a core package of the Python in Heliophysics Community (PyHC), PlasmaPy is included in the Python ecosystems for astronomy and heliophysics. PlasmaPy is used with PyHC packages such as `SpacePy`, `pySPEDAS`, and `Kamodo`, including in the first executable research article in heliophysics (Polson et al. 2023).

We have found that adoption of functionality is most widespread when developed in partnership with a particular subgroup from the plasma community. The most successful examples of this have been with members of the HEDP community. Partnering with collaborator P. Heuer enabled PlasmaPy's Thomson scattering analysis subpackage to become PlasmaPy's most widely used diagnostic functionality (Foo et al. 2023, Zhang et al. 2023, Pilgram et al. 2024, Pokornik et al. 2024, Eisenbach et al. 2025, Valenzuela-Villasaca et al. 2025). **We propose to develop diagnostic and analysis functionality for three subfields of plasma science: experimental magnetized plasma research, HEDP, and heliophysics.** We will develop these capabilities in close coordination with members of these communities. In §4.1, we propose to develop software capabilities needed to analyze data from the most important diagnostics for magnetized plasma experiments in partnership with the MagNetUS community.⁶ In §4.2, we propose functionality to analyze widely-used diagnostics in HEDP experiments, in partnership with UCLA PI D. Schaeffer and Collaborators C. Kuranz and P. Heuer. In §4.3, we propose to partner with PyHC to add functionality needed by the solar and space physics communities. Through these partnerships, we will grow the user and contributor bases of PlasmaPy to improve software sustainability, and enable innovation by providing diagnostic analysis tools that underpin a wide range of scientific research. In §4.4, we outline plans to improve the data environment by developing foundational cyberinfrastructure for plasma science.

Since its inception, the prime challenge faced by the PlasmaPy project has been that **few members of the plasma community have experience contributing to an open source package.** Throughout the first grant period, we encountered significant enthusiasm from members of the community interested in contributing to PlasmaPy. However, their participation was hampered because essential research software engineering skills like version control are rarely covered in plasma coursework. We organized Plasma Hack Week in 2021 & 2022, the inaugural PlasmaPy Summer School in 2024, and frequent live coding tutorials to provide spaces for the plasma community to learn how to use and contribute to an open source package like PlasmaPy. While the situation is improving, more work remains to be done.

We propose to train the next generation of research software engineers (RSEs) in plasma science through a series of educational activities and immersive research experiences. In §5, we describe multiple research and training opportunities for undergraduate and post-baccalaureate students to work directly with team members on projects to enhance PlasmaPy, including in the SPARK program at the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory (SAO) and summer internships at UCLA. We will create a long-term RSE position at UCLA who will become a new long-term core developer of PlasmaPy. Finally, we will forge a partnership between PlasmaPy and the Computational Research Access Network (CRANE) to provide pathways for undergraduates to become computational physicists and RSEs. Through these activities we will solidify the long-term sustainability of PlasmaPy (§7).

2. PlasmaPy: Overview and Current Status

PlasmaPy is a community-driven open source Python package for plasma research and education (PlasmaPy Community 2024). PlasmaPy provides core functionality needed by plasma students and scientists across subdisciplines. It serves as a platform for the plasma community to collaboratively

⁶ MagNetUS is a coalition of user facilities for experimental magnetized plasma research, including BaPSF, WiPPL, the Magnetized Plasma Research Facility (MPRL) at Auburn University, the DIII-D tokamak, PHASMA at West Virginia University, the NRL Space Physics Simulation Chamber.

develop and share needed research software. Development of PlasmaPy prioritizes best practices for scientific computing (Wilson et al. 2014) and writing clean scientific software (Murphy 2023a–b). PlasmaPy has evolved into a robust toolkit that is addressing the software infrastructure needs of plasma science. PlasmaPy’s capabilities range from calculating plasma parameters and transport coefficients to creating synthetic diagnostics for high energy density (HED) plasma. PlasmaPy functionality incorporates and is interoperable with `astropy.units` and/or NumPy arrays. PlasmaPy’s subpackages and capabilities are summarized in the next table. Applications of PlasmaPy are shown in Figs. 1–3 and §3.1.

Subpackage	Description
<code>particles</code>	Provides functional and object-oriented access to particle data, underpinning most of PlasmaPy. Includes the <code>Particle</code> and <code>CustomParticle</code> classes to represent single particles, the <code>ParticleList</code> class to represent a collection of particles, and classes to represent the ionization state for multiple elements in a plasma.
<code>formulary</code>	Enables calculation of a wide variety of fundamental plasma parameters, collision frequencies, laser pulse parameters, and plasma transport coefficients. Draws from and builds upon the widely used NRL Plasma Formulary (Beresnyak 2023).
<code>dispersion</code>	Provides analytical and numerical solutions to the dispersion relations in different regimes that are fundamental to the study of plasma waves and describe how waves propagate at different frequencies and angles from the magnetic field.
<code>analysis</code>	Contains analysis techniques and focused tools applicable to experimental or simulation data, such as for swept Langmuir probe analysis, excess statistics time series analysis, and finding null points in a 3D magnetic field for reconnection studies.
<code>diagnostics</code>	Contains integrated analysis tools for working with real or synthetic data from plasma diagnostics, such as for synthetic charged particle radiography, optical Thomson scattering, and Langmuir probe analysis.
<code>plasma</code>	Contains base classes for representing plasma, such as on a 3D grid.
<code>simulation</code>	Contains the <code>ParticleTracker</code> class and supporting functionality for simulations.
<code>utils</code>	Contains utility functionality used throughout PlasmaPy, such as Python decorators that are used to validate the inputs to most <code>formulary</code> functions.

PlasmaPy’s documentation describes how to use functionality along with the underlying physics. Each function in PlasmaPy has a docstring that follows the numpypdoc standard. The docstrings include a description of what each function does, parameters to be provided to it, return types, and examples showing how it can be used. Docstrings for functions related to plasma concepts include educational notes on the underlying physics. Subpackages such as `plasmapy.particles` also have comprehensive narrative documentation. The gallery of 31 example notebooks introduces how to use PlasmaPy along with associated plasma concepts. PlasmaPy’s documentation is written in reStructuredText, built using Sphinx, hosted on Read the Docs, and tested during each pull request.

PlasmaPy’s documentation has a comprehensive Contributor Guide. This frequently updated guide describes how to contribute, the code contribution workflow, coding best practices, writing/running tests, writing/building documentation, and ways to contribute beyond code. This guide has helped start packages like `WiPPPLy`, and excerpts from it were incorporated into the `pyOpenSci` packaging guide.

PlasmaPy has an extensive test suite to ensure reliability and maintainability. Tests help us find and fix bugs, prevent old bugs from recurring, and provide confidence that code is behaving as expected. This capability lets us change code with confidence that we are not unknowingly introducing bugs elsewhere in the program. PlasmaPy uses `pytest` as its primary test runner, while using the Nox automation tool to ensure that tests are run consistently across platforms. Tests are run for all supported versions of Python and for multiple operating systems. Doctests ensure that docstring examples are correct. About 95% of lines of code in PlasmaPy are covered by at least one of the 4745 tests. PlasmaPy’s continuous integration suite includes linters, autoformatters, static type checking, and other code quality tools.

Fig. 1: This figure from Heuer et al. (2022) compares experimental radiographs with simulated radiographs created using PlasmaPy, highlighting PlasmaPy's capability of allowing users to validate their simulated data results. The top row proton radiographs were created from three different cylindrical implosion experiments conducted at the OMEGA Laser System, and the bottom row synthetic radiographs were generated by supplying electromagnetic fields from 3D radiation hydrodynamics simulations into PlasmaPy's charged particle radiography module.

Fig. 2. A 2D map by Pilgram et al. (2024) of electron density (top) and electron temperature (bottom, mirrored) during a laser-driven shock in an HEDP experiment. These quantities were found using PlasmaPy's Thomson scattering module, and then used to show that the magnetic field was generated via the Biermann battery (a proposed mechanism for the origin of seed magnetic fields in the early universe).

Fig. 3. The temperature ratio between α particles and protons in the solar wind at 1 au. The blue curve is the prediction from applying PlasmaPy's `collisional_analysis` module to *Parker Solar Probe* data. The red-dashed curve shows observations by the *Wind* spacecraft. The similarity shows that preferential heating occurs 0.27 au from the Sun (Johnson et al. 2023).

3. Results from Prior NSF Support

Several members of our team were supported by an NSF CSSI award entitled: *Collaborative Research: Frameworks: An open source software ecosystem for plasma physics*.⁷ Derek Schaeffer is PI of an award entitled *Laboratory Studies of Laser-Driven, Ion-Scale Mini-Magnetospheres on the LAPD*.⁸ Before becoming a non-profit, CRANE activities were funded via the award *CAREER: The Bryn Mawr Plasma Laboratory---A liberal-Arts Centered Facility for Basic Plasma Research and Plasma Science Education*.⁹

3.1. Intellectual merit from prior NSF support

When our original CSSI award began, PlasmaPy was a fledgling package with only two preliminary releases made over a year apart. Since then, we have made 16 feature releases and reduced the time between most releases to ~3 months. We have merged 1488 pull requests since the start of the award and have had 150 unique contributors. PlasmaPy's GitHub repository has been starred 642 times and forked 351 times, indicating broad community interest. Releases of PlasmaPy are on the Python Package Index (PyPI), `conda-forge`, GitHub, and Zenodo (PlasmaPy Community 2024). Total PyPI downloads of PlasmaPy increased by a factor of 2.7 in the past year compared to the year before (Fig. 4). Although this award coincided with a global pandemic, we grew PlasmaPy from a side project into a well-known effort that is enabling innovation across the plasma community. **PlasmaPy is extensively used in heliophysics** (Barnes et al. 2019; DuPont et al. 2020; Qudsi 2021; Maruca et al. 2021; Jara-Almonte et al. 2022; Raymond et al. 2022; Krämer et al. 2023; Polson et al. 2023; Johnson et al. 2023, 2024; Johnson 2024; Wójcik & Macek 2025; Kinoshita et al. 2025; Das & Terres 2025), **high energy density physics (HEDP)** (Pliatskas Stylianidis et al. 2019, Heuer et al. 2022, Davies et al. 2022, Simpson et al. 2023, Foo et al. 2023, H. Zhang et al. 2023, Chen et al. 2024, Pokornik et al. 2024, Pilgram et al. 2024, Daneshmand et al. 2025, Rigon et al. 2024, Eisenbach et al. 2025, Heuer et al. 2025, Y. Zhang et al. 2025, Gao et al. 2025, Valenzuela-Villaseca et al. 2025, Erez 2025; Lee 2025), **laboratory plasma physics** (A. Murphy et al. 2023, L. Murphy 2024, Creamer 2024, Hurst et al. 2025), **astrophysics** (Feinstein et al. 2022), **low temperature plasma science** (Jubin et al. 2024, Córdova-Castillo et al. 2025), and **fusion energy sciences** (Kennedy & Salmonson 2023, González Garmendia 2025).

Fig. 4. Monthly downloads of PlasmaPy from PyPI.

This award enabled extensive improvements to PlasmaPy — both by ourselves and in partnership with the plasma community. We defined the top-level package infrastructure (Everson et al. 2019) and reorganized the `formulary` into its modern form. Undergraduate and graduate students at U. Delaware created `plasmapy.dispersion`, which contains the most commonly used dispersion relations for plasma waves (Alfvén 1942, Stringer 1963, Hollweg 1999, Bellan 2012). We extended `plasmapy.particles` to contain the `CustomParticle` and `ParticleList` classes, and adapted the ubiquitous `@particle_input` decorator to make the `formulary` interoperable with the new objects. We made and supported numerous additions to `analysis` and `diagnostics`, including Langmuir analysis, a magnetic null point finder and classifier, excess statistics time series analysis, charged particle radiography, and Thomson scattering. We overhauled the Contributor Guide to improve sustainability. We modernized packaging and the continuous integration infrastructure, and enabled static type checking. In the next three paragraphs, we highlight examples of how PlasmaPy has enabled scientific innovation.

⁷ This collaborative project included NSF awards 1931388 to the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory (PI: N. Murphy, \$1,439,530), 1931429 to UCLA (PI: S. Vincena, \$539,583), 1931393 to Bryn Mawr College (PI: D. Schaffner, \$187,240), and 1931435 to U. Delaware (PI: B. Maruca, \$273,452) with a period of performance from 2019-10-01 to 2025-09-30 including a 1 year no-cost extension.

⁸ NSF award 2320946 to UCLA was for \$499,999 from 2023-04-01 to 2025-11-30.

⁹ NSF award 1846943 to Bryn Mawr College was for \$564,631 from 2019-08-15 to 2025-12-31.

We worked with Dr. Heuer to add a module in `plasmaPy.diagnostics` for **charged particle radiography** — a technique used to diagnose the structure of electric and magnetic fields in high energy density plasmas (Heuer et al. 2022, Schaeffer et al. 2023). The area of interest is positioned between a bright source of protons and a detector. Electromagnetic fields deflect particles as they pass through the plasma, producing patterns on the detector. PlasmaPy’s `charged_particle_radiography` module can be provided with electromagnetic fields defined on a 3D grid to produce a synthetic radiograph. By using PlasmaPy to create synthetic radiographs from a numerical simulation and comparing them to experimental radiographs, researchers can validate the simulation and ascertain whether the physical model is complete or missing important effects. For example, Heuer et al. (2022) found that their simulations were able to reproduce large-scale structures but were missing small-scale features (Fig. 1).

Thomson scattering is a plasma diagnostic that provides reliable localized measurements of the density, temperature, and energy distribution function of electrons (Finch et al. 2021). In this technique, a laser beam induces elastic interactions between photons and free electrons that scatter light. With Dr. Heuer, we added the `thomson` module to `plasmaPy.diagnostics` to perform fits of the Thomson scattered power spectrum to provide localized electron temperature and density. Pilgram et al. (2024) used this module to create a 2D map of the electron density and temperature during a laser-driven blast wave in an experiment (Fig. 2). Their results demonstrate that the measured magnetic field was created via the Biermann battery — a mechanism proposed as the origin of magnetic fields in the early universe.

PlasmaPy is used to address key questions in heliophysics such as: how is the solar wind heated? Different ion species are commonly observed to have different temperatures in the weakly collisional solar wind. For example, ${}^4\text{He}^{2+}$ ions (α particles) in the solar wind often have a higher temperature than protons. Ion temperature ratios provide important constraints on plasma heating mechanisms in the solar wind. This award enabled recent U. Delaware graduate student E. Johnson to create PlasmaPy’s `collisional_analysis` module from his thesis research (Johnson 2024). Dr. Johnson added functionality to model the evolution of ion temperature ratios of a plasma in transit due to particle collisions. By applying this functionality to observations from *Parker Solar Probe* and comparing it to observations from *Wind*, Dr. Johnson found the important constraint that most preferential heating between α particles and protons occurs within 0.27 au of the Sun (Fig. 3; Johnson et al. 2024).

Prof. Schaeffer developed a novel high-repetition-rate platform at UCLA for studying ion-scale magnetospheres that combined the magnetized plasma of the LAPD and high-powered laser driver from the Phoenix Laser Laboratory with a pulsed dipole magnet. Initial experiments demonstrated the creation of a laser-driven ion-scale magnetosphere (Schaeffer et al. 2022), which were well-matched by comprehensive 2D PIC simulations (Cruz et al. 2022). Follow-on numerical studies identified the mechanisms by which the laser-driven plasma couples energy into the background plasma (Cruz et al. 2023), a critical component for generating the laboratory magnetosphere. Recent experiments further demonstrated driven magnetic reconnection and the first 3D volumetric measurements of magnetic and electric fields in an ion-scale magnetosphere using the same platform (Rovige et al. 2024).

3.2. Broader impacts from prior NSF support

PlasmaPy has consistently been connected to the larger plasma community and strives for broader engagement. At the 2020 APS-DPP meeting, we organized a mini-conference called Growing an Open Source Software Ecosystem for Plasma Science. This mini-conference had talks on PlasmaPy, software citation, open hardware, metadata standards, and plasma software. We led the organization of Plasma Hack Week in 2021 and 2022, which had a peak attendance of ~100 people each year. These events included structured tutorials on how to use and contribute to PlasmaPy (now available on PlasmaPy’s YouTube channel), as well as unstructured hack sessions as opportunities to put the lessons into practice. The hack sessions in 2022 were an opportunity for participants to contribute to a “hack formulary” akin to `plasmaPy.formulary`. Some functions added to the hack formulary were later incorporated into PlasmaPy. We began weekly virtual office hours during the pandemic so the community could engage with us directly, with frequent attendance from students. At APS DPP meetings from 2022–2025, we hosted in-person exhibitor booths that allowed us to engage with ~200–250 attendees each year.

We led multiple tutorials annually, covering various forums, topics, and audiences. We gave PlasmaPy tutorials at the Summer Undergraduate Laboratory Internship (SULI) Introduction to Fusion Energy and Plasma Physics Course from 2021–2025, with videos available on the SULI website. Dr. Murphy led tutorials at the PyHC summer schools in 2022 and 2024, and at multiple meetings and institutions from 2022–2025. Dr. Murphy gave Python tutorials for solar REU students at SAO and presented on *Making Plasma Science Open* at the Computational Physics School for Fusion Research at MIT from 2021–2024 (Murphy 2023c). Dr. Murphy frequently presented on *Writing Clean Scientific Software*, including a widely attended Exascale Computing Project webinar (Murphy 2023a). Dr. Murphy gave a plenary talk on PlasmaPy at the inaugural Open Source Software for Fusion Energy conference in 2025, and provided multiple intermediate and advanced tutorials to fellow RSEs in PyHC.

The final major event of the award was a fully in-person PlasmaPy Summer School held at Bryn Mawr College in July 2024. The primary goal of the school was to train a potential new group of PlasmaPy contributors. We solicited applications from the plasma community and chose 25 participants from 82 applications. Each participant was provided full travel funding through the award. The attendees were chosen based on potential for contribution to the PlasmaPy project, and ranged from undergraduates to tenured faculty. The school incorporated lessons from previous Hack Weeks and tutorials on effective RSE education. Lessons covered submitting pull requests, coding best practices, writing tests, and how to use PlasmaPy subpackages. The school included a discussion on code review best practices as well as multiple participant-driven unconference sessions inspired by PyCon.

This award enabled us to play an important and ongoing role in workforce development. We advised multiple students, including one undergraduate and two graduate students at U. Delaware, two undergraduate interns at SAO, six students at Bryn Mawr College, and one Plasma and Fusion Undergraduate Research Opportunities (PFURO) intern. We regularly create GitHub issues and label them as “good first issue” along with labels describing difficulty levels. These issues are often used by newcomers to learn how to contribute to an open source project.

CRANE was funded via an NSF CAREER supplement to Bryn Mawr to conduct three cycles of their 16-week free online Python course from 2023–2025. The three cycles served 297 total students, among whom 57 received a stipend for their participation. Stipends were also provided to instructors and TAs. The CRANE curriculum includes an Introduction to Python (Part 1), Numerical Methods (Part 2), and Advanced Algorithms (Part 3). The Part 3 options for CRANE students in 2026 are Monte Carlo methods, Magnetohydrodynamics with FLASH, Machine Learning, Astronomy Data Analysis, Signal and Image Processing, Particle-in-Cell Simulations, and Open Science & Research Software Engineering. Several CRANE students were provided with one-on-one mentorship with CRANE leads, which often continued after the cycle ended. In post-program survey evaluations, the vast majority of students felt that they learned to code in a supportive environment, and almost all felt comfortable teaching introductory Python to a peer and that they were provided an opportunity to develop their research skills.

Prof. Schaeffer’s mini-magnetosphere project supported workforce development at the postdoctoral, graduate, and undergraduate levels. A postdoc was trained in all aspects of experimental design and data analysis, while a master’s student was trained on numerical simulations. A graduate student is currently being trained on experiments for this project. Four undergraduate students were mentored as part of summer or independent research courses. This project is providing experience to a high school student as part of a collaboration with a local high school. Results from this project were highlighted for a broad public audience in AIP News and New Scientist.

4. Proposed Software Development Activities

In this section, we propose five major priorities from PlasmaPy’s software development roadmap that we will undertake in this effort.¹⁰ We will prioritize contributions based on community input and feedback. All

¹⁰ We do not include software development activities solely related to fusion energy sciences (FES) in this proposal because such tasks are traditionally under the purview of the Department of Energy rather than NSF. However, we will coordinate with and provide support to members of the FES community on their contributions and include them in the educational activities described in §5.

extensions to PlasmaPy's capabilities will include documentation and tests, and most will include example Jupyter notebooks. Except in performance critical locations, functionality will be compatible with `astropy.units`. Throughout this project, we will support new users and contributors; advise students as described in the Mentoring Plan; hold weekly meetings; provide constructive code reviews; and partner with MagNetUS, PyHC, and the HEDP community. Investigator responsibilities and the timeline of deliverables are included in the Management and Coordination Plan.

4.1. Magnetized Laboratory Plasma Diagnostics

Laboratory experiments are crucial to answering **science-driven** questions about fundamental plasma processes—e.g., what controls wave–particle energy transfer, turbulent transport, reconnection rates, shock formation, and dynamo action—under conditions where cause-and-effect can be isolated and quantitatively tested. This includes plasma waves (e.g., Vincena et al. 2024), plasma turbulence (Schaffner et al. 2012), magnetic reconnection (Yamada et al. 2010), collisionless shock formation (Niemann et al. 2014), dynamos (Cooper et al. 2014), particle acceleration (Yoo et al. 2014), and the magnetorotational instability (Ji & Goodman 2023). Experiments provide insights into the solar corona heating problem (Bose et al. 2024), coronal mass ejections (Bryant et al. 2024), auroral acceleration (Schroeder et al. 2021), and accretion disks (Ji & Goodman 2023). These insights are enabled by direct, time-resolved, multi-point probe measurements in a controlled setting. Across these drivers, progress is limited less by diagnostic availability than by the lack of standardized, validated, interoperable analysis tools that convert raw data into comparable physical quantities with uncertainties and metadata.

We will expand PlasmaPy to deliver **community-grade** analysis for widely used diagnostics that collectively measure key quantities of interest. We will implement new functionality for magnetic probes (time-varying magnetic field structure), Mach probes (flow velocity), emissive probes (plasma potential), hairpin probes (local electron density), laser-induced fluorescence (ion temperature and velocity distribution functions), and microwave interferometry (line-integrated electron density), while extending existing Langmuir probe (plasma potential, electron temperature, density) and Thomson scattering (electron density and temperature; see §4.2) capabilities. PlasmaPy will incorporate analysis techniques from well-cited literature (Hutchinson 2002; Chen et al. 2012; McWilliams & Edrich 2003; Kunze, 2009). We focus on this subset because it is broadly applicable across plasma platforms—from dusty and low-temperature plasmas to industrial tools, thrusters, cathodes, helicons, compact toroid injectors, and magnetic confinement devices—maximizing impact across the science topics above.

Although analysis codes exist for many diagnostics, they are frequently re-written by successive students and may remain inconsistent even within a single laboratory. By providing well-tested, community-validated tools, PlasmaPy will **reduce duplication of effort and enable reproducible, cross-device comparisons** that directly support validation of theory and simulation. This effort will improve knowledge transfer, accelerate consistent analysis cycles, and broaden the parameter space over which diagnostic methods are tested.

PlasmaPy will provide two varieties of analysis tools: (1) focused tools which reside in `plasmapy.analysis`, and (2) integrated tools which reside in `plasmapy.diagnostics`. Focused tools are well-defined, single-purpose functions that calculate a given parameter for a given diagnostic. These functions are designed around NumPy arrays and prioritize computational efficiency. Integrated tools are `xarray` accessors and expand upon the focused tools. The `diagnostics` subpackage provides a more complete analysis environment that (1) collects all related diagnostic focused tools, (2) incorporates diagnostic metadata, (3) incorporates a centralized structure (`xarray.Dataset`) for data and metadata management, and (4) provides quick visualization tools. To think of it another way, `analysis` includes functionality analogous to `sin()` and `cos()`, while `diagnostics` performs specific tasks analogous to plotting points in a circle. **Together, these layers support both rapid hypothesis testing (focused tools) and end-to-end, reproducible diagnostic workflows (integrated tools).**

Nearly all new incorporated plasma diagnostics will have functionality in both focused and integrated tools, with focused analysis tools being developed first. This approach will: (1) lower the workload barrier for development and inclusion of new plasma diagnostic tools, (2) provide an analysis workflow that includes standardized diagnostic metadata, and (3) provide options for a user's own personal workflow.

Critically, it allows users to innovate: researchers can extend focused tools for new regimes, add device-specific metadata, and compose integrated workflows without rewriting the foundations.

To date, we have prioritized focused analysis tools. In the next development cycle we will expand on those tools while implementing the integrated tools framework and populating functionality. We will add analysis functionality and educational notebooks for the diagnostics most commonly used in laboratory plasma experiments: hairpin probes, Mach probes, magnetic flux probes, emissive probes, interferometry, and laser-induced fluorescence. Any remaining time will be used to add spectroscopic diagnostics using functionality from `specutils` (an affiliated package of Astropy). **These deliverables directly map to the measurement needs of the above science drivers (fields, flows, density/temperature, and distribution functions), enabling faster iteration between experiment, model, and simulation.**

To enhance code usability we will focus on the continued implementation of an intuitive package structure, clean interfaces, and quick data visualization. An intuitive package structure increases discoverability of functionality. Clean interfaces are designed with explicitly named functionality and arguments, similarly named conceptual arguments across subpackages, and well-tailored arguments and functions that do singular tasks. Quick plotting routines will be implemented using `matplotlib` so analysis results can be visualized and interpreted early and frequently in the analysis process. Visualization tools will be developed for both focused and integrated analysis tools. **By lowering the time from measurement to interpretable physics, these capabilities broaden participation, accelerate scientific throughput, and empower users to build new diagnostic workflows on a shared, validated foundation.**

4.2. High Energy Density Physics

We propose to expand PlasmaPy to include (1) toolkits to collectively analyze data from most widely used HEDP diagnostics, and (2) educational resources such as Jupyter notebooks. PlasmaPy currently has modules for two critical HEDP diagnostics: optical Thomson scattering (OTS), which provides localized measurements of electron density & temperature, and charged particle radiography (CPR), which is the only practical means of measuring electromagnetic fields in high energy density (HED) plasma. We propose to expand these modules by adding new HEDP diagnostic analysis capabilities along with associated educational materials. The selected diagnostics were chosen because they are both common in HED experiments and are more analytically tractable than others within HEDP.

We will expand PlasmaPy's OTS capabilities and allow fitting of the non-Maxwellian distributions that are common in HED plasma. The `thomson` module includes forward modeling and fitting of Thomson scattering spectra assuming Maxwellian velocity distributions. We will update this to include any user-supplied velocity distribution. We will update the OTS spectral fitting routine to allow reconstructions of plasma parameters from data collected from non-Maxwellian plasmas. As part of the fitting routine, we will explore adding new optimization algorithms beyond those currently included (e.g., automatic differentiation) that may be better suited to the large number of free parameters inherent in non-Maxwellian distributions. This will allow scientists to extract plasma parameters from a broader range of HED experiments, especially in kinetic-scale and collisionless regimes.

PlasmaPy's current CPR module is limited to forward modeling of synthetic images from supplied 3D electromagnetic field configurations. **We will expand the CPR module to add reconstruction algorithms that can take collected data (e.g., proton flux images) and return path-integrated electromagnetic field profiles.** Several models exist for reconstructions, from relatively simple ODE solvers for 1D reconstructions to more sophisticated Monge-Ampere algorithms for 2D reconstructions. We will implement at least one 1D and one 2D solver. Given the importance of measuring electromagnetic fields for a wide range of phenomena, such reconstructions are very common in HEDP.

We will add **refractive imaging** capabilities to PlasmaPy, including both **shadowgraphy** and **angular filter refractometry** (a variation of schlieren imaging). Refractive imaging measures 2D density profiles and is especially useful for measuring large density gradients such as those found in HED shock experiments. We will add both forward models and reconstruction algorithms for these diagnostics. We will add capabilities for **particle energy spectrometers** that utilize magnets to disperse particles in space based on their energy distribution. These are one of the primary ways to measure energetic particles in

HED plasmas. We will add a module that will include routines for processing image plate data and calibrating the energy response of the spectrometer based on an input magnetic field profile.

The addition of these capabilities will help address forefront questions in HEDP science, especially within the field of laboratory astrophysics, where all of these diagnostics are commonly used. Phenomena such as collisionless shocks and magnetic reconnection are ubiquitous in astrophysical systems and can now be recreated in laboratory experiments; however, they often require a kinetic-scale description to address fundamental questions about how particles and fields interact, and so will benefit from the added OTS, CPR, and refractive imaging capabilities that allow scientists to analyse data in this regime. Likewise, these phenomena are associated with non-thermal particle distributions and particle acceleration that remain poorly understood theoretically, and so will benefit from new capabilities that allow analysis of particle spectrometer data of energetic particles. As we implement these capabilities, we will coordinate with the NSF Zetawatt-Equivalent Ultrashort pulse laser System (ZEUS), a recently-completed HED facility, via Prof. Kuranz. ZEUS is developing OTS, particle radiography, and refractive imaging diagnostics, so the expanded tools will allow ZEUS users to quickly process and analyze data while providing feedback for further module development in PlasmaPy.

We will concurrently develop educational notebooks that complement the existing and added HEDP capabilities. The notebooks will serve as learning aids for the functionality of these HEDP diagnostics, the physics behind them, and the science that can be done with them. For example, for the OTS module, we would develop notebooks that demonstrate how to forward model non-Maxwellian velocity distributions, derive the Thomson scattering cross section, and calculate jump conditions across a shock that was diagnosed with OTS in an experiment.

4.3. Interoperability with the Python environment for heliophysics

The mission of the **Python in Heliophysics Community** (PyHC) is to facilitate scientific discovery by promoting the use and development of sustainable open source software across the solar and space physics community. Because the Sun and heliosphere are plasma, PlasmaPy has been a core package of PyHC since 2019 (along with SunPy, SpacePy, pySPEDAS, pysat, Kamodo, and *fiasco*). Dr. Murphy has represented PlasmaPy in PyHC since 2018. The biggest challenge facing PyHC has been to foster interoperability. This challenge is particularly difficult because most PyHC packages were developed independently and pre-date PyHC by several years. A few PyHC packages — including SunPy, PlasmaPy, and *fiasco* — are growing a pocket of interoperability by leveraging Astropy. We propose a series of tasks to improve interoperability between PlasmaPy and PyHC.

We will create `plasmapy.distribution` to host classes that describe analytical and discretized velocity distribution functions (VDFs). Particles in a plasma commonly follow a VDF that departs significantly from a Maxwellian. Non-Maxwellian VDFs in space, laboratory, and HED plasmas provide a window into a rich variety of collisionless plasma processes like wave-particle interactions, particle acceleration, shocks, reconnection, turbulence, energy transport and conversion, and microinstabilities. We will deprecate the `formulary` functions for kappa and Maxwellian VDFs in favor of classes in `plasmapy.distribution` for each type of distribution function. The `Maxwellian`, `BiMaxwellian`, and `KappaDistribution` classes will accept quantities such as temperature, bulk velocity, particle, and dimensionality as arguments. These classes will have methods for the VDF; cumulative distribution function; mean, most probable, and root mean square speeds; variance; skewness; excess kurtosis; and entropy. We will create a class for a discretized VDF with a similar API, along with methods to fit the distribution function to an analytical VDF, view pitch angle distributions (relative to the magnetic field), and determine stability. These classes will include visualization methods and educational docstrings. Finally, we will create a class to represent a time series of discretized distribution functions.

We will incorporate non-equilibrium ionization modeling capabilities from PlasmaPy-NEI into `fiasco`. Collaborator W. Barnes created *fiasco* (Barnes et al. 2024) to be a Pythonic interface to the CHIANTI atomic database, which is widely used by solar physicists to analyze spectra and model atomic processes. This package is interoperable with older capabilities from `plasmapy.particles`. We will work with Dr. Barnes to make *fiasco* interoperable with PlasmaPy's `ParticleList` and

`IonizationState` data structures. When a plasma undergoes a rapid change in temperature, it takes some time for ionization and recombination reactions to bring the ionization state distribution back to equilibrium. If a hydrogen plasma starts off at 10^4 K with an ionization fraction of 1% and is instantaneously heated to 10 MK, then it could take minutes to hours for the plasma to become 100% ionized. In the meantime, the plasma is in non-equilibrium ionization (NEI). NEI effects must be modeled to accurately interpret *in situ* observations of the solar wind, and remote observations of both coronal mass ejections (CMEs) and supernova remnant shock waves. Using NEI forward modeling in conjunction with remote or *in situ* observations lets us constrain the thermal history of plasma (e.g., Murphy et al. 2011). PlasmaPy-NEI is an affiliated package that performs highly customizable NEI modeling of plasma, and has been used to constrain plasma heating in the solar wind and CMEs (DuPont et al. 2020, Wilson et al. 2023). However, PlasmaPy-NEI lacks functionality to predict spectral line emission. Incorporating PlasmaPy-NEI's modeling capabilities into `fiasco` will simplify the prediction of spectral line emission, and thus greatly reduce the difficulty of comparing the models to observations. This task will leverage `fiasco`'s existing capabilities and improve sustainability by reducing the overall maintenance burden.

We will add functionality to read spacecraft data into PlasmaPy data structures. Space missions such as *Solar Orbiter* and the *Advanced Composition Explorer* have instruments that directly measure the composition of the solar wind (i.e., the ionization states for different elements). We will create functionality to read composition data into `IonizationState` data structures that can be directly compared to the results of NEI modeling in `fiasco`. We will similarly create functionality to read VDF data into the new data structure for discretized distribution functions. We will prioritize missions with widely used data, and leverage an existing CDF file reader such as `cdflib` or `spacepy.pycdf`.

4.4. Improving the data environment for plasma science

One of the most significant barriers to making plasma science open is its data environment (Murphy 2023c). While open access data sets are common in heliophysics and astronomy, very few data sets from laboratory plasma physics are openly available. Data sets are developed independently by each facility and thus lack interoperability. For example, suppose we are performing similar experiments at two different facilities: BaPSF and WiPPL. Because the data sets were designed in isolation from each other, we have to learn multiple data formats and write separate software to perform the same analysis.

A metadata standard is an agreed-upon framework that dictates how metadata should be created, structured, and maintained. Metadata standardization is essential for making scientific data sets findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR; Wilkinson et al. 2016). Metadata standards ensure that data sets are machine-readable and human-understandable. The data environment in fundamental plasma science is difficult to navigate because (1) few metadata standards exist, and (2) very few data sets follow a metadata standard. The lack of standardization inhibits innovation by making it harder to find relevant data sets, understand data sets acquired at other facilities, collaborate with other researchers, perform machine learning studies, and write general purpose scientific software.

In the last few years, open metadata standards have begun emerging in fundamental plasma science and HEDP. **OpenPMD** is a metadata standard that provides naming and attribute conventions for particle and mesh based data, in particular from PIC simulations.¹¹ OpenPMD has been adopted by at least 17 plasma simulation codes. **Plasma-MDS** is a metadata standard for research data in plasma science and technology (Franke et al. 2020). This schema describes how to include information about plasma source, medium, and target; plasma diagnostics; and simulation/modeling methods. Plasma-MDS has been adopted in multiple projects, including the Interdisciplinary Plasma Technology Data Platform. There are also specialized metadata standards such as **pradformat** for CPR data and metadata standards under active development such as the Helmholtz Laser-Plasma Metadata Initiative (**HELPMI**) for ultra-high intensity laser plasma experiments. The Integrated Modeling & Analysis Suite (**IMAS**) for the International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor (ITER) includes a newly released metadata standard for magnetic

¹¹ Particle-in-cell simulations are used to investigate the wide range of plasma phenomena that cannot be described with a fluid model, including shocks, magnetic reconnection, plasma wave propagation and interactions, turbulent heating in the solar wind, laser-plasma interactions, and instabilities.

confinement fusion devices that may be extensible to magnetized laboratory plasma experiments. To our knowledge, these are the only open metadata standards that exist for laboratory plasma science.

The plasma science community is now recognizing the importance of adopting open metadata standards, as judged by community reviews and reports (NASEM 2021, APS DPP CPP 2020, FESAC 2020, LaserNetUS 2023, Anirudh et al. 2022, Feister et al. 2023, Gruber et al. 2023) and even organizational bylaws (MagNetUS 2022). Despite this recognition, adoption of metadata standards at experimental plasma research facilities has been very limited. With the exception of openPMD, few software tools exist to read, validate, and write plasma data sets following these standards. It is therefore very difficult at present for facilities to adopt a metadata standard, and most lack the time and resources to attempt this.

We propose to implement and improve functionality in PlasmaPy to interact with plasma data sets that follow existing and emerging open metadata standards. PlasmaPy contains a `Plasma` factory class that was added by a former Google Summer of Code student. Like SunPy's core `Map` class, instantiation of `Plasma` will cause it to choose the appropriate subclass based on the contents and structure of the file provided to it (Leonard 2018). The original implementation contains a subclass for HDF5 files for the basic version of the openPMD standard. We will update the implementation of the openPMD subclass to include the six extensions to openPMD that have been added since the original implementation. When possible, we will leverage existing Python tools for working with openPMD files. We will add `Plasma` subclasses that contain a reader, validator, and writer for HDF5 files that follow each of the Plasma-MDS, pradformat, and HELPMI standards. Implementation of the IMAS standard would use existing tools such as `omas` or `imas-python`. As metadata standards are implemented, we will prioritize interoperability with the `analysis`, `diagnostics`, `formulary`, and `plasma` subpackages, as well as `astropy.units`. Metadata standards are independent of file format, so we will implement back-ends for different file types such as netCDF if needed to meet the needs of experimentalists. Because few laboratory plasma data sets are standardized, we will decouple diagnostic analysis functionality from the front-end implementation of these standards. In particular, the focused tools in §4.1 will have well-defined signatures that accept NumPy arrays, with clear examples in docstrings and example notebooks to show how non-standardized data can be analyzed.

We will work with the MagNetUS community to improve its data environment. As the inaugural chair of the Data and Software Working Group, Dr. Murphy built a working relationship with people at most MagNetUS facilities. We will request sample data sets from MagNetUS facilities including MPRL, PHASMA at West Virginia University, BaPSF (courtesy of Dr. Vincena), and the Bryn Mawr Plasma Laboratory (courtesy of Dr. Schaffner). We will use the functionality described above to reorganize data files to follow Plasma-MDS or the IMAS standard. We will request sample ZEUS data sets and convert them into the HELPMI standard. We will share methods for standardizing data sets with each facility, and provide tutorials at MagNetUS meetings on how to use this functionality. We will also participate in planning discussions for potential new facilities such as the CHIMERAS project (Dorfman et al. 2025). These activities will provide the foundational cyberinfrastructure necessary for studies that make use of data from multiple facilities, including machine learning studies.

4.5. Package infrastructure

Regular maintenance is vital to the health of software. We will regularly perform maintenance and improve package infrastructure throughout this project.¹² We will routinely update code, tests, and documentation after breaking changes and deprecations in upstream packages. We will place high priority on fixing bugs reported by users. The Python packaging landscape is rapidly evolving, and we will periodically update packaging infrastructure and the release process to follow emerging best practices and improve contributor experience. We will periodically refactor existing code to reduce cognitive complexity, mitigate performance bottlenecks, and ensure that PlasmaPy remains portable to high performance computing (HPC) applications. We will regularly update the Contributor Guide to be consistent with current package, testing, and documentation infrastructure.

¹² Package infrastructure and maintenance activities in years 1 & 2 will be covered by NASA award 80NSSC25K0360 (PI: Murphy) for two months per year.

5. Proposed Research Software Engineering Training Activities

We will lead frequent tutorials on PlasmaPy, research software engineering, and open science to the plasma community. We will provide regular tutorials on PlasmaPy at events such as the annual APS DPP meeting, MagNetUS meetings, PyHC summer schools, and the SULI introductory course. We will invite attendees to contribute to PlasmaPy. We will upload tutorial videos to YouTube. We will expand tutorial notebooks into full lessons in the style of The Carpentries to enable tutorials to be led by others. We will create intermediate & advanced tutorials for subpackages and newly implemented diagnostics. Each year we will provide frequent virtual tutorials for the plasma community to learn how to contribute to an open source package.

We will provide numerous opportunities for students to work directly with team members on contributions to PlasmaPy. Dr. Murphy will advise multiple students through the post-baccalaureate Student Pathway to Astrophysical Research Knowledge (SPARK) program at SAO. SPARK students will work on year-long projects such as dispersion relation solvers for plasma waves (Xie 2014, Xie & Xiao 2014, Verscharen & Chandran 2018), equilibrium and stability analysis (Bernstein et al. 1958, Tajima 2004), plasma turbulence analysis techniques (e.g., Fujisawa 2010), and magnetic topology visualization (Haynes & Parnell 2007, 2010). UCLA team members will advise two undergraduates per year on summer projects. We will prioritize opportunities for these students to learn essential RSE skills.

5.1 Computational Research Access Network (CRANE)

This project will support five cycles of the annual 16-week free online Python course run by the Computational Research Access Network (CRANE).¹³ CRANE is a non-profit led by graduate students, postdocs, and early-career scientists mostly from the plasma community who each spring provide a series of weekly virtual seminars on computational physics geared towards undergraduate and graduate students who have expressed interest in physics and astronomy. CRANE has run four annual cycles of the course with a fifth cycle starting in January 2026. Lessons are conducted via Zoom and use Google Colab. Course materials are developed by the early-career members of CRANE who serve as course instructors and teaching assistants. **The CRANE budget request includes funding to provide stipends to CRANE students during the workshop.** Post-surveys have shown that these stipends double student retention. Project PIs will add lessons based on feedback from CRANE students and the project team members. These resources, classes, and workshops are open to all students and scientists. However, a significant audience for CRANE has been low income, first-generation college students from high schools and colleges with limited or no access to computational physics, so the program is designed to expect zero computational background from students. The stipends will allow CRANE students to participate who were otherwise unable to due to employment, childcare, or other commitments.

The CRANE curriculum teaches introductory Python, numerical methods, foundational computational skills, and advanced algorithms — all foundational skills needed for computational physics and astronomy research. The Introduction to Python section includes Boolean logic, loops, functions, and plotting. The numerical methods section includes the Euler Method, Runge-Kutta Method, Finite Difference Method, and built-in Python solvers to solve introductory mechanics and electromagnetism problems such as projectile motion, pendulum motion, and the Lorentz Force. Since these problems have analytic solutions, CRANE shows how scientists approximate solutions using numerical methods. Just like how PlasmaPy uses numerical solvers to approximate solutions, the students learn how these numerical solvers work so that they can use them in their future computational research equipped with an understanding of the underlying numerical methods. The foundational skills the students learn include using the Linux terminal with `bash` commands, collaborative project management using `git` and GitHub, and scientific writing with LaTeX. These skills are invaluable to students aspiring to perform computational research or physics software development.

¹³ This task addresses the following recommendation from the most recent plasma decadal review (NASEM 2021): “Federal agencies (e.g., DOE, NSF, NASA, DoD) should structure funding to support undergraduate and graduate educational, training, and research opportunities—including faculty—and encourage and enable access to plasmas physics”.

Learning these skills prepare students for the advanced tracks in CRANE, which include PIC methods, Monte Carlo, machine learning, astronomy data analysis, magnetohydrodynamics with the FLASH code, signal and image processing, and open science & research software engineering (a new track led by Dr. Murphy with tutorials on version control, software testing, and creating a Python package with `uv`). These tracks run in parallel and students can take one or more of them. We will add a new advanced CRANE track on PlasmaPy. Subpackages like `plasmapy.formulary` would fit well into a new CRANE/PlasmaPy track since they encompass plasma physics topics used across different subfields. This track will also include new and existing diagnostic analysis capabilities from §4.1 and §4.2, such as Langmuir probe analysis and HEDP diagnostics. The track will prepare students for a research software engineering project in plasma science. **We will recruit current and former CRANE students for year-long post-baccalaureate SPARK training opportunities at SAO.** The chance for CRANE students to learn these skills and cement them with a long-term immersive research experience would be invaluable for recruiting and retaining students while training the next generation of RSEs. Forging a partnership between CRANE and PlasmaPy will improve the sustainability of both efforts.

6. Broader Impacts

This project will lay a foundation for open and reproducible plasma science. Reproducibility and transparency are cornerstones of the scientific method and gold standard science. Unfortunately, the scientific reproducibility best practices that are rapidly being adopted in fields like psychology and astrophysics have yet to be widely adopted in plasma physics (Murphy et al. 2019b, Murphy 2023c). The predominant closed science practices inhibit reproducibility by making it extremely hard for researchers to replicate results or to reconcile differences between experiments. PlasmaPy will do necessary work to make plasma research transparent and reproducible. Implementation of readers, validators, and writers for emerging plasma metadata standards is vital to making laboratory plasma data sets findable, accessible, interoperable, and reproducible (FAIR; Wilkinson et al. 2016). We are proposing to engage in a multi-year effort to develop foundational cyberinfrastructure to make plasma data sets FAIR in order to improve reproducibility, increase transparency, enhance discoverability, greatly reduce the difficulty of performing archival and machine learning projects that use data from multiple facilities, allow data to be used to its fullest potential, and thus enable innovation.

The PlasmaPy ecosystem enables the plasma community to pool resources and enhance collaborations within and across disciplines. Historically, each MagNetUS user facility has developed its own software stack to analyze experimental data, leading to significant duplication of effort and a severe lack of interoperability. Guest investigators at one facility have had to learn new software and data storage conventions if they are awarded time at a different facility. It has therefore been unnecessarily difficult to perform the same analysis on multiple experiments. A shared software ecosystem will reduce both costly duplication of effort and the difficulty of comparing results from different experiments. Similarly, experimentalists and spacecraft observers who study similar phenomena currently operate in quite distinct software environments, making comparisons between the two unnecessarily difficult. A unified software approach will save time and resources as well as foster more efficient and collaborative research within the plasma community. PlasmaPy reduces the need to rewrite functionality that already exists but is hard to read, inadequately documented, or closed source. Researchers that reuse existing code will not have to spend time rewriting what has already been written. This broader impact will be fully realized by training the next generation of RSEs in plasma science via the educational activities described above.

Growing the PlasmaPy ecosystem will broaden access to plasma research and education to all Americans. Realizing the full potential of this ecosystem will ensure that students can get off to a fast start for their first research projects. Continued growth and adoption of PlasmaPy will enable students and scientists at small institutions to not only have the same access to plasma research software as flagship institutions, but also contribute to it. PlasmaPy is already enabling undergraduates to learn common analysis techniques for plasma research such as Langmuir analysis (A. Murphy et al. 2023, L. Murphy 2024, Creamer 2024) and even perform innovative machine learning studies (Eisenbach et al. 2025). Our continued work will provide researchers at small schools with access to cutting-edge research tools developed in collaboration with scientists at major plasma institutions.

Expanding PlasmaPy functionality will reduce the software development burden needed to establish small-scale experiments. In recent years, there has been an increase in the number of plasma laboratories developed outside flagship institutions. The Small College Plasma Consortium (SCPC) is a coalition of small, predominantly undergraduate, and liberal arts colleges with faculty who conduct plasma research. Since faculty at these schools interface mostly with undergraduate students, supporting plasma education at these locations is particularly impactful for workforce development. When building a small-scale plasma experiment, a time-consuming but often overlooked task is to create the software needed to analyze the results. Continued growth of PlasmaPy will substantially reduce the software development overhead while providing undergraduate researchers with access to well-documented code and multiple example notebooks. This benefit will be greatest at small institutions and institutions with limited resources, such as members of the SCPC. **As a free resource, PlasmaPy can be utilized by fusion energy startups and small businesses focused on plasma diagnostics.**

PlasmaPy is growing into an important freely available educational resource for plasma science. PlasmaPy docstrings not only describe how to use a function or class, but also the underlying physics. In some cases, `formulary` docstrings have information that is currently missing from Wikipedia (such as for the Buchsbaum frequency). The docstrings are supplemented by a gallery of Jupyter notebooks which use PlasmaPy to introduce plasma concepts and analysis techniques. We will expand the gallery to include a systematic progression of notebooks for use in introductory courses.¹⁴ We will partner with educators in the plasma community who will use the notebooks in actual courses, including in CRANE and the SCPC. We will connect to other fields by adding lessons to Learn Astropy and the PyHC gallery.

7. Long-term Software Sustainability

Since its inception, we have continually progressed toward the long-term sustainability of PlasmaPy. Key institutional knowledge is shared among multiple people. We wrote a comprehensive Contributor Guide to streamline onboarding of new contributors, and have well-defined governance. We have fully documented and mostly automated the release process. PlasmaPy has an excellent suite of continuous integration checks, and a reliable mechanism to rapidly find and fix problems arising from breaking changes in upstream dependencies via automated weekly pull requests (such as #2909 in PlasmaPy's repository). We provided tutorials to hundreds of people during our prior CSSI award, including two plasma hack weeks and the PlasmaPy Summer School. We trained multiple undergraduates and graduate students to make contributions to PlasmaPy over an extended period. Prof. Schaffner has incorporated research software engineering lessons into his physics courses. PlasmaPy development has been funded by multiple sources, including NSF, NASA, DOE, the Smithsonian Institution, and Google Summer of Code. As described in the Management and Coordination Plan, **we will improve long-term software sustainability by updating our open source governance policies and joining NumFOCUS.**

We will solidify software sustainability through training the next generation of RSEs in plasma science and engineering. CRANE will provide lessons on computational physics to hundreds of students over the course of the project. We will encourage CRANE students to apply to the post-baccalaureate SPARK program. The SPARK students will spend a year contributing to PlasmaPy and learning essential research software engineering skills that they will take to their next institution. We will invite each incoming SPARK student to join PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee for a three-year term that extends beyond the conclusion of their year-long project. SPARK students often continue to graduate school in the same field, making it likely that they will continue as active members of the PlasmaPy community for years to come.

¹⁴ This task addresses the following recommendation from the most recent plasma decadal review (NASEM 2021): *“Computational plasma science and engineering, supported by NSF, should include projects for writing textbooks and developing courses to train the current and next generation of computational plasma scientists, and to enable noncomputer experts to make optimal use of computations.”*

Management and Coordination Plan

Team Member Roles and Responsibilities

Nicholas Murphy (PI: SAO) will coordinate project activities; monitor project deliverables; serve on PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee; advise SPARK students; provide user and contributor support; perform code reviews; organize community meetings, tutorials, and workshops; lead the development of the `particles`, `distribution`, `formulary`, and `plasma` subpackages; lead software development tasks related to heliophysics, fundamental plasma science, and the data environment; assist with diagnostic analysis functionality; coordinate with the Python in Heliophysics Community (PyHC); maintain PlasmaPy's Contributor Guide; perform code maintenance; improve package infrastructure; engage with the plasma community; and develop educational materials.

The **SPARK students** at SAO will engage in year-long post-baccalaureate research software engineering projects to add fundamental plasma science functionality into PlasmaPy. Probable topics include analytical & discretized particle distribution functions, plasma wave dispersion relations, time series turbulence analysis techniques, and plasma equilibrium & stability analysis tools. SPARK students will learn research software engineering techniques; contribute code, documentation, & tests; perform code reviews; and serve on PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee.

David Schaffner (PI: Bryn Mawr College) will oversee the educational endeavors of the project (including development of tutorial notebooks for use in plasma courses) and assist in the development of `diagnostics` functionality for magnetized laboratory plasma experiments. He will serve as the primary administrator for website and exhibitor needs for the annual American Physical Society (APS) Division of Plasma Physics (DPP) meeting. He will serve as a point of contact between PlasmaPy and CRANE, and engage with the Small College Plasma Consortium.

Imani West-Abdallah (subaward PI: CRANE) will coordinate CRANE activities as described in this proposal, manage CRANE's subaward from Bryn Mawr College, serve as a point of contact between CRANE's board of directors and PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee, and advertise SAO's post-baccalaureate SPARK program to CRANE students.

Derek Schaeffer (PI: UCLA) will oversee the overall activities of the project at UCLA, coordinate UCLA's activities with the PIs at collaborating institutions, and oversee the development of high energy density physics (HEDP) functionality in the `diagnostics` and `analysis` subpackages. He will supervise the RSE at UCLA; co-advise students; and coordinate with MagNetUS and ZEUS.

Stephen Vincena (Co-PI: UCLA) will oversee the development within `diagnostics` for magnetized laboratory plasma experiments, provide technical expertise about plasma diagnostics to the research software engineer and other project participants, and co-advise student participants.

The **research software engineer** (RSE) at UCLA will be the lead developer of the `diagnostics` and `analysis` subpackages for both HEDP and magnetized laboratory plasma diagnostics. The RSE will provide user and contributor support, co-advise student participants, develop educational notebooks, give tutorials, provide constructive code reviews, improve software infrastructure, and serve on PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee.

Will Barnes (collaborator) is a Research Assistant Professor at American University and the Deputy Lead Developer of SunPy. Dr. Barnes is the creator of `fiasco`: a Pythonic interface to the CHIANTI atomic database used in solar physics. Dr. Barnes will share technical expertise on `fiasco`, CHIANTI, and SunPy; collaborate on PlasmaPy and `fiasco` integration; and provide code reviews.

Peter Heuer (collaborator) is an experimental plasma physicist at the Laboratory for Laser Energetics at the University of Rochester and a frequent contributor to PlasmaPy. As the original author of the `charged_particle_radiography` and `thomson` modules, Dr. Heuer will share expertise on these modules and other HEDP diagnostics, and provide code reviews.

Carolyn Kuranz (collaborator) is a Co-PI of the NSF Zetawatt-Equivalent Ultrashort pulse Laser System (ZEUS) at the University of Michigan. She will coordinate linkages between PlasmaPy and ZEUS and share expertise on HEDP diagnostics.

Project Timeline

Major tasks in this proposal are included in the following Gantt chart:

We will perform software maintenance and research software engineering training activities throughout the project. We will prioritize analytical & discretized particle distribution functions (§4.3) because they are needed for the Thomson scattering, plasma wave dispersion solver, particle spectrometers, laser-induced fluorescence (LIF), and non-equilibrium ionization (NEI) tasks. The data environment task (§4.4) includes expansion of the `Plasma` class factory to implement the openPMD, Plasma-MDS, HELPMI, and pradformat metadata standards; applying these tools to actual data sets; writing documentation & tests; and giving tutorials. The projects for the SPARK students are representative, and may change to better fit the prior experience and long-term goals of each student. We may host an SPARK student in the 2026–27 academic year if given sufficient lead time. HEDP diagnostics (§4.2) include charged particle radiography (CPR) reconstruction, Thomson scattering, particle spectrometers, shadowgraphy, and refractometry. The *in situ* plasma diagnostics for magnetized laboratory plasmas (§4.1) include implementing analysis functionality for magnetic flux probes, Mach probes, emissive probes, and hairpin probes and improving existing functionality for Langmuir probes.

PlasmaPy Governance

The defining documents for the project are PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposals (PLEPs). PLEPs are used to propose major changes to PlasmaPy; describe governance policies and practices of PlasmaPy; and provide information to the PlasmaPy community. PLEPs are created on GitHub and openly archived on Zenodo. PLEPs provide an opportunity for all members of the plasma community to guide the direction of the PlasmaPy project.

PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee oversees and manages project activities. The responsibilities of the Coordinating Committee are described in PLEP 2, and are to make major decisions (including decisions of PLEPs), coordinate and delegate tasks, facilitate community-wide communication, oversee code development, manage PlasmaPy repositories, regulate intercompatibility, and enforce the code of conduct. We will actively recruit frequent contributors, collaborators, and enthusiastic volunteers to officially join the Coordinating Committee. Day-to-day decisions on code development and community events do not go through the Coordinating Committee, and are instead made after informal discussions or on GitHub. The PlasmaPy community abides by version 3.0 of the Contributor Covenant Code of Conduct.

We will improve the long-term sustainability of PlasmaPy by updating governance policies and joining NumFOCUS. PLEP 2 was last revised in 2018 when the project was significantly smaller. We will update PLEP 2 in year 1 to better reflect current practices and adopt innovations in open source governance such as those made by Astropy in 2021 (e.g., a clear definition of Voting Members) and SunPy in 2024 (e.g., their definition of Project Custodians). We will then apply to join NumFOCUS — a non-profit dedicated to supporting open source scientific software projects. Joining NumFOCUS as a sponsored project will increase community visibility of PlasmaPy while providing access to administrative support, eligibility for tax-deductible donations, fundraising infrastructure, and liability protection.

Coordination Mechanisms

We will hold weekly PlasmaPy community meetings to coordinate software development activities, perform code reviews, plan educational activities, and share knowledge. These virtual meetings are open to all, and advertised on PlasmaPy's website, online documentation, and GitHub repository. We will hold regularly scheduled working group meetings for topics such as plasma diagnostics and educational activities. Dr. Murphy and the RSE will host virtual office hours as an opportunity for users and contributors to interact with core developers, and for core developers to get feedback from community members.

We will onboard new members of the project by providing a series of tutorials. We will meet with them multiple times per week during their first month to fully introduce their projects. New members will have access to the extensive Contributor Guide in PlasmaPy's online documentation, and the opportunity to pair program with senior members. Advisors will have frequent one-on-one meetings with students, and be available at other times for informal discussions and rapid code reviews. Both students and advisors will participate in community meetings and working group meetings. We will use Discord as the platform for online group discussions.

We will continue to plan software development activities via GitHub issues, pull requests, discussions, and projects. For each project to be performed by a student, senior members of the team will create a GitHub issue with a detailed description of their project before they arrive, along with sub-issues for more concrete tasks. These issues will include the plasma physics background, helpful hints, implementation plans, and links to important references. Each non-trivial pull request will undergo a code review by at least one other team member, including students. Each pull request must pass multiple checks prior to merging — including tests, documentation builds, linters, code quality tools, and static type checking.

CRANE leadership meets weekly and uses Slack to coordinate CRANE activities. PlasmaPy team members will join these meetings to discuss partnership activities as needed. Through these meetings, CRANE and PlasmaPy team members will work together to develop new advanced tracks focusing on PlasmaPy subpackages and research software engineering skills.

Meetings, Workshops, and Travel

We will hold in-person PlasmaPy workshops at the annual meetings of MagNetUS and the American Physical Society (APS) Division of Plasma Physics (DPP). These workshops will include tutorials, collaboration meetings, Coordinating Committee meetings, and/or open hack sessions. We plan to propose mini-conferences at the APS DPP meeting on topics such as growing an open source software ecosystem for plasma science or improving the plasma science data environment for artificial intelligence and machine learning. The budgets include travel funding for collaboration visits. For example, Dr. Murphy will visit UCLA and Bryn Mawr multiple times over the duration of the project, and the RSE will visit Dr. Murphy annually for collaboration purposes.

We will continue to reserve an exhibitor booth at each APS DPP meeting to engage with ~200–250 plasma students and scientists each year. These booths provide an opportunity to demonstrate PlasmaPy, answer questions, receive community feedback (including frequent feature requests), and provide in-person support.

Data Management and Sharing Plan

Research products

The primary research products of this project will be the **code, documentation,¹ and tests of PlasmaPy and related packages**. We will create research products such as **presentations, articles, tutorials, and websites.²** We will use **data sets** for tutorials, testing, calibration, and functionality needed by users. We will extend existing **metadata standards** if necessary.

Licensing

PlasmaPy research products will continue to be released under permissive open source licenses to maximize the potential for use, modification, dissemination, and scientific reproducibility. PlasmaPy is developed openly on GitHub³ under the permissive **BSD 3-clause** open source license to maximize license compatibility. This license permits relicensing and allows proprietary derivative works, which removes barriers to technology transfer and commercial applications associated with copyleft licenses such as the GPLv3. Similarly, `fiasco` is available under the BSD 3-clause license.

Publications, presentations, data sets, and other research products will be made openly available under Creative Commons licenses. We will use the **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license** for most of these research products. The CC BY 4.0 license allows redistribution and modification of a creative work so long as attribution is provided and an indication is given if changes were made. The attribution requirement ensures that provenance information remains available in derivative works. If a research product incorporates material that is licensed under a copyleft license (such as the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License; CC BY-SA 4.0), then the derivative research product will be released under the license of the incorporated work.

The licenses for the metadata standards to be implemented are CC BY 4.0 for Plasma-MDS and openPMD, CC BY-SA 4.0 for HELPMI, and the MIT license for `pradformat`. These standards are developed on GitHub with releases available on Zenodo.

Versioning

PlasmaPy uses calendar versioning of the form `YYYY.M.PATCH`, where `YYYY` represents the year, `M` represents the month without a trailing zero, and `PATCH` represents the patch or bugfix number. For example, `v2025.10.0` was the first release of PlasmaPy in October 2025.

Availability

PlasmaPy is developed openly on GitHub. Anyone with internet access can view and search through the entire code development history of the project (including all 975 issues and 2137 pull requests as of November 2025). The PlasmaPy organization includes GitHub repositories

¹ PlasmaPy's online documentation: <https://docs.plasmapy.org>

² PlasmaPy project website: <https://www.plasmapy.org>

³ PlasmaPy GitHub repository: <https://github.com/PlasmaPy/PlasmaPy>

for tutorials, PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposals, the PlasmaPy project website, the 2024 PlasmaPy Summer School, and non-equilibrium ionization modeling.

PlasmaPy releases are made available on the Python Package Index (PyPI) and conda-forge. Releases are available on GitHub, and are uploaded to the PlasmaPy Community on Zenodo⁴ so that each release has a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) as its persistent identifier. The release process is described in our Delivery Mechanism and Community Usage Metrics. We will continue openly uploading presentations, community papers, proposals, technical reports, and other research products to the PlasmaPy Community on Zenodo. Videos of tutorials will be uploaded to platforms such as YouTube, Zenodo, and Twitch to reach a broad audience.

Dependency management

PlasmaPy's v2025.10.0 core dependencies are `astropy`, `h5py`, `lmfit`, `matplotlib`, `mpmath`, `numpy`, `packaging`, `pandas`, `requests`, `scipy`, `tqdm`, `wrapt`, and `xarray`. These packages are available under permissive open source licenses. PlasmaPy follows the SPEC⁵ 0 recommendations to support minor releases of dependencies released in the past 24 months and Python releases in the last 36 months. SPEC 0 allows releases to be dropped early due to bugs, vulnerabilities, or important new features. Support for older releases continues when needed for interoperability with shared environments and platforms like Google Colab.

The Python environment used in most continuous integration tests and documentation builds is defined in a lockfile (`uv.lock`). PlasmaPy's repository includes a workflow to update the lockfile via a weekly automated pull request to provide an opportunity to fix new failures caused by breaking changes in upstream dependencies and prevent spontaneous new failures in unrelated pull requests. The continuous integration suite includes running tests against the minimum versions of direct dependencies using `uv`'s `lowest-direct` resolution strategy.

Security

PlasmaPy's security policy is located in its GitHub repository at `.github/SECURITY.md`. This policy includes a mechanism to privately report security vulnerabilities. PlasmaPy's continuous integration suite includes multiple automated checks for vulnerabilities. Vulnerabilities in GitHub workflows are identified with `zizmor`. Vulnerabilities in Python code are identified via `ruff`'s `flake8-bandit` rule set. Pull requests are scrutinized for suspicious code during code review.

We will expand PlasmaPy's security policy and finish implementing the SPEC 6 recommendations on access to restricted resources, such as documenting resources, assigning the lowest privileges for each contributor to do their work meaningfully, making project assets accessible to ≥ 2 maintainers, and storing secrets in a secure encrypted remote location.

We will implement the SPEC 8 recommendations on securing the release process by pinning third-party GitHub workflows to full commit SHAs, switching from using authentication tokens to PyPI Trusted Publishers,⁶ and using GitHub Attestations to increase supply chain security of builds. We will expand the security policy to address contributions made using generative AI.

⁴ PlasmaPy Community on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/plasmapy>

⁵ Scientific Python Ecosystem Coordination (SPEC): <https://scientific-python.org/specs>

⁶ PyPI Trusted Publishers: <https://docs.pypi.org/trusted-publishers>

Mentoring Plan

This project includes support for post-baccalaureate students to participate in the Student Pathway to Astrophysical Research Knowledge (SPARK) program at the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory (SAO). This program enables recent graduates to carry out a research project under the guidance of SAO scientists, often prior to applying to graduate school. In some cases, the participant may be a visiting graduate student enrolled in the SAO Predoctoral Program.

Each participant will be responsible for learning and performing research software engineering (RSE) activities for PlasmaPy. SPARK students will have opportunities to participate in multiple professional development opportunities at SAO each month. SAO participants will become members of the solar physics group at the CfA. We will recruit participants who are interested in becoming RSEs, including students from the Computational Research Access Network (CRANE).

Upon arrival, each participant will attend an **orientation session** to become acclimated to the institution and project. They will then have an in-depth discussion with their new advisor about potential areas of learning and growth in the next year, career goals, specific objectives, and professional development opportunities. They will collaborate and agree upon an action plan — for both student and advisor — that will be periodically revisited. While the SPARK students will be advised directly by Dr. Murphy, all proposal team members will participate in their mentorship. Dr. Murphy will meet with each SPARK student ~1–3 times per week and be available for more frequent informal discussions and quick turnaround code reviews.

Because plasma courses rarely cover RSE skills, the **onboarding** process will emphasize developing the skills for contributing to open source projects like PlasmaPy via one-on-one tutorials with senior members of the team. They will have access to the extensive Contributor Guide in PlasmaPy's online documentation which covers the code contribution workflow, coding conventions & best practices, software testing, and writing documentation. Participants will make pull requests of gradually increasing complexity to explore different aspects of PlasmaPy such as documentation, tests, & package infrastructure. They will have opportunities for pair programming with senior members of the team. Because all planned projects require some knowledge of plasma physics, senior members of the team will engage in multiple one-on-one discussions to introduce the scientific background and context behind each project.

We will encourage participants to engage in **professional development** activities related to their educational and career goals, including tutorials and seminars on a variety of topics organized by the SPARK program. Participants will be able to attend conferences (such as the annual meeting of the APS Division of Plasma Physics) and summer schools (such as the Python in Heliophysics Community Summer School) related to their interests. We will introduce the participants to our colleagues in the field at these events to ensure sufficient **networking opportunities**.

We will provide opportunities for participants to learn **teaching and mentoring skills**. We will encourage them to attend mentoring workshops and become certified as instructors for Software Carpentry. We will invite participants to co-lead live coding tutorials for PlasmaPy, and encourage them to participate in CRANE as a lecturer, teaching assistant, and/or mentor.

We will provide each student with **leadership opportunities**. We will invite each student to join the Coordinating Committee so they can guide the future of PlasmaPy, and to continue in that role after the conclusion of their year-long project. Students will have the option to join or lead a working group for PlasmaPy and become a maintainer of a subpackage. We will encourage them to establish collaborations, organize events, develop tutorials, and present their work. We will continue to provide mentorship after the successful conclusion of their project.

CI Professional Mentoring and/or Professional Development Plan

This proposal requests funding to hire a **research software engineer (RSE)** at UCLA. The RSE will be responsible for developing `plasmapy.diagnostics`, providing user and contributor support, co-advising students, developing educational materials, giving tutorials, providing constructive code reviews, improving software infrastructure, and serving on PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee. The RSE will be supervised by Prof. Schaeffer and work closely with Dr. Murphy, Dr. Vincena, and members of the Basic Plasma Science Facility (BaPSF) at UCLA.

The RSE will work at the interface between software engineering, science, and education. They will therefore require mentoring and professional development opportunities in multiple areas. Dr. Murphy will mentor the RSE on research software engineering and plasma physics. Prof. Schaeffer, Dr. Vincena, and Prof. Schaffner will mentor the RSE on plasma diagnostics, high energy density physics, and plasma physics. Prof. Schaffner will mentor the RSE on the educational aspects of the project.

Soon after the RSE is welcomed into the project, we will invite them to discuss their professional goals and identify potential growth areas with Prof. Schaeffer, Dr. Vincena, and Dr. Murphy. The outcome of these discussions will be a **professional development plan** tailored to the RSE to help them not only excel at their job responsibilities but also realize their long-term professional goals. These discussions will also let us fine tune the following onboarding process, which includes training in both research software engineering and plasma science. We will revisit the professional development plan approximately twice per year.

Dr. Murphy will visit UCLA shortly after the RSE's arrival to provide one-on-one **training on research software engineering** and how to use and contribute to PlasmaPy. The training will begin with PlasmaPy's origin story and then continue with tutorials on `astropy.units`, `plasmapy.particles`, `plasmapy.formulary`, the code contribution workflow, and functionality in PlasmaPy intended for use by contributors rather than end users. The RSE will make initial contributions while engaging in pair programming with Dr. Murphy. Dr. Murphy will provide additional training to the RSE on the technology stack used in PlasmaPy development and cover topics such as software testing with `pytest`, writing documentation with `reStructuredText` and `Sphinx`, managing Python projects with `uv`, using `pre-commit`, type hint annotations, and setting up continuous integration workflows with `Nox` and `GitHub Actions`. Dr. Murphy and the RSE will also discuss best practices in research software engineering such as how to write clean scientific software, providing constructive code reviews, and test-driven development. The RSE will have access to the extensive Contributor Guide in PlasmaPy's online documentation and will be provided with a copy of this proposal.

The RSE will receive **training on plasma diagnostics** from Prof. Schaeffer and Dr. Vincena throughout the project to prepare them for their role as the primary developer of

plasmapy.diagnostics. While much of the training on research software engineering topics will be front-loaded, the training on the scientific aspects will continue throughout the project. This onboarding process will begin with a broad overview of high energy density physics, laboratory plasma physics, and plasma diagnostics. The RSE will then be provided with a deep dive into one particular diagnostic that they will focus on as their first project. The RSE will be provided with one or more sample data sets from that diagnostic, and go through the process of analyzing each data set to gain experience with interpreting data from that diagnostic. After gaining these skills, they will use their experience to design and implement software in PlasmaPy to perform these analyses. This process will repeat for each diagnostic. We will encourage the RSE to collaborate directly with researchers who use the functionality that they developed to get experience writing research articles.

The RSE will have the opportunity to receive **training on teaching and mentorship** held at UCLA. They will then gain experience in these skills by co-advising and co-mentoring undergraduate interns along with Prof. Schaeffer and/or Dr. Vincena, and providing mentorship to SPARK students at SAO. We will encourage the RSE to become certified as a Software Carpentry instructor to learn best practices for teaching research software engineering skills and leading live coding tutorials.

The RSE will gain **leadership and organizational experience** by becoming a member of PlasmaPy's coordinating committee, co-advising students, and leading a working group on plasma diagnostics. We will provide the RSE with opportunities to participate in writing grant proposals, including as the principal investigator.

The RSE will be provided with **networking opportunities** through attending conferences such as the annual meeting of the American Physical Society Division of Plasma Physics. The RSE will present their work on PlasmaPy at each APS DPP meeting. We will encourage the RSE to join the US Research Software Engineer (US-RSE) Association, which is the primary professional organization for RSEs in the US. Participation in US-RSE will provide them with the opportunities to network with RSEs at other institutions and attend tutorials on intermediate and advanced research software engineering topics.

Delivery Mechanism and Community Usage Metrics

Deliverables

The principal ongoing deliverables of this project are **quarterly releases of PlasmaPy** with **new functionality, documentation, and tests**. Additional ongoing deliverables include **tutorials, guides, presentations, technical reports, and journal articles**. For testing or documentation purposes, some **data sets** may be created or compiled. The primary services to be rendered are **user support, contributor support, and tutorials** on how to use or contribute to PlasmaPy and affiliated packages.

Specific software deliverables include: diagnostic functionality to analyze data from hairpin probes, Mach probes, magnetic flux probes, emissive probes, interferometry, and laser-induced fluorescence; improved Thomson scattering fitting capabilities; reconstruction algorithms for charged particle radiography; refractive imaging analysis capabilities (including shadowgraphy and angular filter refractometry); analysis of particle energy spectrometer data; functionality to read, validate, and write plasma data sets that follow the Plasma-MDS, openPMD, pradformat, and HELPMI metadata standards; classes to study analytical and discretized velocity dispersion functions in laboratory & space plasmas; non-equilibrium ionization modeling capabilities in fiasco; functionality to read in space plasma data sets into PlasmaPy data structures; magnetic topology visualization functionality; and plasma equilibrium/stability analysis tools. All functionality will have tests and documentation, often in the form of example Jupyter notebooks. The timeline for these deliverables is included in a Gantt chart in the Management and Coordination Plan.

Specific service deliverables include regularly scheduled community meetings and office hours, along with multiple tutorials on PlasmaPy and research software engineering per year.

Delivery mechanisms

Official releases of PlasmaPy will continue to be made available on the Python Package Index (PyPI) for installation using `pip` or `uv`, and `conda-forge` for installation with `conda`.

PlasmaPy has a GitHub workflow that is manually triggered to create an issue containing the instructions and checklist for each release (e.g., issue #3127 on PlasmaPy's GitHub repository). The release checklist includes code quality updates, running regular and comprehensive tests, performing the release on GitHub, and post-release tasks. The release process itself is mostly automated and takes only a few minutes. When a release is created on GitHub, it triggers a GitHub workflow that uploads the release to the Python Package Index (PyPI). A release on PyPI triggers a pull request (PR) to the `conda-forge` feedstock. Once this PR is merged, the release becomes available via `conda-forge`. The release is uploaded to the *PlasmaPy Community* on Zenodo¹ and assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). PlasmaPy's online documentation² is hosted by Read the Docs. This includes the documentation for the stable release, past releases, and the latest version available on GitHub.

Research articles will be published in open access journals like the *Journal of Plasma Physics* or with an open access option. Tutorials, guides, presentations, PLEPs, technical reports, and data sets will all be openly available on GitHub, Zenodo, and/or PlasmaPy's online documentation.

Please see the Data Management and Sharing Plan for PlasmaPy's licensing practices and our plans to improve supply chain security during the release process.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/plasmapy>

² <https://docs.plasmapy.org>

Metrics

We will use download statistics from PyPI and conda-forge as a proxy to gauge relative trends in PlasmaPy usage. PyPI monthly download statistics are available from Google BigQuery as a public dataset (see Fig. 4 in the Project Description). Interpretation of these statistics must keep in mind that most downloads from PyPI are automated (e.g., for use in continuous integration testing), the accuracy of download data is limited (due to mirrors, caching, and changes in technology), and that monthly download data is very noisy.

We will perform an annual survey of PlasmaPy's user and contributor communities for our primary usage metric. This survey will inquire about the frequency of PlasmaPy usage, preferred subpackages, how they learned about PlasmaPy, desired features, and the quality of any experiences contributing to the project (including contributions beyond code). We will disseminate the survey through PlasmaPy's email newsletter, other communication channels, and various plasma community forums and newsletters. To triple the number of users inferred from survey respondents, we target an increase of ~25% annually.

We will use SciX to track research articles that cite or acknowledge usage of PlasmaPy.³ The Science Explorer (SciX) is a digital library portal for researchers in astronomy, physics, heliophysics, planetary science, and Earth science. SciX makes it straightforward to track citations to PlasmaPy research products. We will use SciX to track articles that cite or acknowledge usage of PlasmaPy, add them to a dedicated bibliography on PlasmaPy's website. Because most research journals in plasma science lack a clear software citation policy, PlasmaPy's documentation includes instructions on how to cite and acknowledge PlasmaPy to increase the completeness of this metric.

Readily available **statistics from GitHub** will help us assess usage, community interest, code development effectiveness, and the health of PlasmaPy's contributor base. Specific metrics include the number of issues raised or resolved; PRs created or merged; lines of code changed; the number of stars and forks of the repository; the total number of contributors; and the number of unique contributors per year. To achieve our target of tripling the number of yearly contributors over the five-year project, we will need to increase the number of unique contributors by ~25% annually.

We will create a GitHub repository to automate collection and visualization of usage metrics. Google BigQuery, GitHub, and SciX each have a public Application Programming Interface (API). We will create Python scripts to retrieve the appropriate data, and then create GitHub workflows to update the data and visualizations.

We will qualitatively assess development by determining whether the most pressing capabilities are being created, bugs are being fixed, documentation is being written and maintained, pull requests are promptly being reviewed, new code is readable and maintainable, and the test suite is thorough and meets code quality standards.

Program Assessments

CRANE will continue to compare the results of pre- and post-program surveys to assess the efficacy of each cycle. Recent surveys have included questions about how confident students are in their ability to learn computational tools and techniques (86% of post-program survey respondents), whether CRANE allowed them to learn to code in a supportive environment (93%), and if they could picture themselves in a research career (86%). CRANE will use feedback from these surveys to improve the program for subsequent cycles.

³ The Science Explorer (SciX) is "a digital library portal for researchers in astronomy, Earth science, heliophysics, physics, and planetary science" that indexes "software, data, and projects funded by NASA and the NSF." SciX is the successor to NASA's Astrophysics Data System (ADS).

References

- H. Alfvén (1942). Existence of Electromagnetic-Hydrodynamic Waves. *Nature*, 150, 405, <https://doi.org/10.1038/150405d0>
- American Physical Society Division of Plasma Physics Community Planning Process (APS DPP CPP 2020), A Community Plan for Fusion Energy and Discovery Plasma Sciences, available from <https://sites.google.com/pppl.gov/dpp-cpp> with a preprint at <https://arxiv.org/abs/2011.04806>
- Astropy Collaboration, A. M. Price-Whelan, P. L. Lim, N. Earl, N. Starkman, L. Bradley, D. L. Shupe, A. A. Patil, L. Corrales, C. E. Brasseur, M. Nöthe, A. Donath, E. Tollerud, B. M. Morris, A. Ginsburg, E. Vaher, B. A. Weaver, J. Tocknell, W. Jamieson, M. H. van Kerkwijk, T. P. Robitaille, B. Merry, M. Bachetti, H. M. Günther, T. L. Aldcroft, J. A. Alvarado-Montes, A. M. Archibald, A. Bódi, S. Bapat, G. Barentsen, J. Bazán, M. Biswas, M. Boquien, D. J. Burke, D. Cara, M. Cara, K. E. Conroy, S. Conseil, M. W. Craig, R. M. Cross, K. L. Cruz, F. D'Eugenio, N. Dencheva, H. A. R. Devillepoix, J. P. Dietrich, A. D. Eigenbrot, T. Erben, L. Ferreira, D. Foreman-Mackey, R. Fox, N. Freij, S. Garg, R. Geda, L. Glattly, Y. Gondhalekar, K. D. Gordon, D. Grant, P. Greenfield, A. M. Groener, S. Guest, S. Gurovich, R. Handberg, A. Hart, Z. Hatfield-Dodds, D. Homeier, G. Hosseinzadeh, T. Jenness, C. K. Jones, P. Joseph, J. B. Kalmbach, E. Karamahmetoglu, M. Kałuszyński, M. S. P. Kelley, N. Kern, W. E. Kerzendorf, E. W. Koch, S. Kulumani, A. Lee, C. Ly, Z. Ma, C. MacBride, J. M. Maljaars, D. Muna, N. A. Murphy, H. Norman, R. O'Steen, K. A. Oman, C. Pacifici, S. Pascual, J. Pascual-Granado, R. R. Patil, G. I. Perren, T. E. Pickering, T. Rastogi, B. R. Roulston, D. F. Ryan, E. S. Rykoff, J. Sabater, P. Sakurikar, J. Salgado, A. Sanghi, N. Saunders, V. Savchenko, L. Schwardt, M. Seifert-Eckert, A. Y. Shih, A. S. Jain, G. Shukla, J. Sick, C. Simpson, S. Singanamalla, L. P. Singer, J. Singhal, M. Sinha, B. M. Sipócz, L. R. Spitler, D. Stansby, O. Streicher, J. Šumak, J. D. Swinbank, D. S. Taranu, N. Tewary, G. R. Tremblay, M. de Val-Borro, S. J. Van Kooten, Z. Vasović, S. Verma, J. V. de Miranda Cardoso, P. K. G. Williams, T. J. Wilson, B. Winkel, W. M. Wood-Vasey, R. Xue, P. Yoachim, C. Zhang, A. Zonca, Astropy Project Contributors (2022). The Astropy Project: Sustaining and Growing a Community-oriented Open-source Project and the Latest Major Release (v5.0) of the Core Package, *Astrophysical Journal*, 935, 167, <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac7c74>
- J. Auerbach; S. G. Bilén (2025). Multi-Diagnostic Investigation of a 3D-printed Electrode within an Inertial Electrostatic Confinement Thruster, 39th International Electric Propulsion Conference.
- W. T. Barnes, S. J. Bradshaw, N. M. Viall (2019). Understanding Heating in Active Region Cores through Machine Learning. I. Numerical Modeling and Predicted Observables, *Astrophysical Journal*, 880, 56, <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab290c>
- W. T. Barnes, D. Stansby, N. Murphy, J. Reep, S. Mumford, N. Freij, L. Hayes (2024). fiasco, version 0.3.0post, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10476096>
- A. Beresnyak (2023). NRL Plasma Formulary. Naval Research Laboratory (Plasma Physics Division), <https://www.nrl.navy.mil/News-Media/Publications/nrl-plasma-formulary>
- I. B. Bernstein, E. A. Frieman, M. D. Kruskal, R. M. Kulsrud (1958). An energy principle for hydromagnetic stability problems, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London*, A24417, 40, <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.1958.0023>
- S. Bose, J. M. TenBarge, T. Carter, M. Hahn, H. Ji, J. Juno, D. Wolf Savin, S. Tripathi, S. Vincena (2024). Experimental Study of Alfvén Wave Reflection from an Alfvén-speed Gradient Relevant to the Solar Coronal Holes, *Astrophysical Journal*, 971, 72, <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ad528f>
- K. Bryant, R. P. Young, H. J. LeFevre, C. C. Kuranz, J. R. Olson, K. J. McCollam, C. B. Forest (2024). Creating and studying a scaled interplanetary coronal mass ejection, *Physics of Plasmas*, 31, 042901, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0187219>

- Burrell, A. G.; Halford, A.; Klenzing, J.; Stoneback, R. A.; Morley, S. K.; Annex, A. M.; Laundal, K. M.; Kellerman, A. C.; Stansby, D.; Ma, J. (2018). Snakes on a Spaceship—An Overview of Python in Heliophysics. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 12, 10384, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JA025877>
- C. Chen, E. S. Lavine, W. M. Potter, C. E. Seyler, B. R. Kusse (2024). Axial confinement of wire array Z-pinch precursor plasmas by a pulsed magnetic mirror field, *Physics of Plasmas*, 31, 072704, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0207561>
- F. F. Chen, J. D. Evans, W. Zawalski (2012). Calibration of Langmuir probes against microwaves and plasma oscillation probes, *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* 21 055002, <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/0963-0252/21/5/055002>
- C. M. Cooper, J. Wallace, M. Brookhart, M. Clark, C. Collins, W. X. Ding, K. Flanagan, I. Khalzov, Y. Li, J. Milhone, M. Nornberg, P. Nonn, D. Weisberg, D. G. Whyte, E. Zweibel, C. B. Forest (2014). The Madison plasma dynamo experiment: A facility for studying laboratory plasma astrophysics, *Physics of Plasmas*, 21, 013505, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4861609>
- L. Córdova-Castillo; I. Camps; A. Figueroa; S. Cuevas (2025). Local analysis of a DC glow discharge in an inverted coaxial diode, *Vacuum*, 241, 114654, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vacuum.2025.114654>
- L. Creamer (2024), Dimensionlessly Comparing Hydrogen and Helium Plasmas at LAPD, Undergraduate Honors Thesis, William & Mary, <https://scholarworks.wm.edu/honorstheses/2228>
- Cruz, F. D.; Schaeffer, D. B.; Cruz, F.; Silva, L. O. (2022). Laser-driven, ion-scale magnetospheres in laboratory plasmas. II. Particle-in-cell simulations. *Physics of Plasmas*, 29, 032902, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0084354>
- Cruz, F. D.; Schaeffer, D. B.; Cruz, F.; Silva, L. O. (2023). Strong collisionless coupling between an un-magnetized driver plasma and a magnetized background plasma. *Physics of Plasmas*, 30, 052901, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0144725>
- L. A. Daneshmand, M. Aszalos, S. Feister, J. R. Smith (2025). Intensity and dimensionality-dependent dynamics of laser-proton acceleration in 1D, 2D, and 3D particle-in-cell simulations, *Physics of Plasmas*, 32, 023908, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0234889>
- S. B. Das; M. Terres (2025). Recovering Ion Distribution Functions: II. Gyrotropic Slepian Reconstruction of Solar Wind Electrostatic Analyzer Measurements, *arXiv:2511.05415*, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2511.05415>
- J. R. Davies; P. V. Heuer (2022). Evaluation of direct inversion of proton radiographs in the context of cylindrical implosions, *arXiv:2203.00495*, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.00495>
- J. R. Davies; P. V. Heuer, A. F. A. Bott (2023). Quantitative proton radiography and shadowgraphy for arbitrary intensities, *High Energy Density Physics*, 49, 101067, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hedp.2023.101067>
- S. Dorfman, S. Bose, E. Lichko, M. Ablter, J. Juno, J. TenBarge, Y. Zhang, S. C. Thakur, C. Cartagena-Sanchez, P. Tatum, E. Scime, G. Joshi, S. Greess, C. Kuchta (2025). The CHIMERAS project: design framework for the Collisionless High-beta Magnetized Experiment Researching Astrophysical Systems, *Journal of Plasma Physics*, 91, 4, E121, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022377825100469>
- M. DuPont, C. Shen, N. A. Murphy (2020). Comparative Analysis of the Solar Wind: Modeling Charge State Distributions in the Heliosphere, *arXiv:2012.12297*, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2012.12297>

- S. Eisenbach, D. A. Mariscal, R. S. Dorst, T. Van Hoomissen, A. M. Ortiz, H. Zhang, J. J. Pilgram, C. G. Constantin, L. Rovige, P. V. Heuer, D. B. Schaeffer, C. Niemann (2025). Machine learning analysis of high-repetition-rate two-dimensional Thomson scattering spectra from laser-produced plasmas, *Journal of Physics D Applied Physics*, 58, 035202, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/ad89d6>
- I. N. Erez (2025). Flux Compression for Magnetized Warm Dense Matter. Ph.D. thesis, University of Rochester, ProQuest Dissertations & Theses, 32244148
- E. T. Everson, T. Parashar; S. Vincena, N. A. Murphy (2019), PLEP-0007 — Structure of Top-Level Sub-packages. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3774573>
- E. T. Everson (2024). bapsflib, <https://pypi.org/project/bapsflib>
- A. D. Feinstein, K. France, A. Youngblood, G. M. Duvvuri, D. J. Teal, P. W. Cauley, D. Z. Seligman, E. Gaidos, E. M.-R. Kempton, J. L. Bean, H. Diamond-Lowe, E. Newton, S. Ginzburg, P. Plavchan, P. Gao, & H. Schlichting (2022). AU Microscopii in the Far-UV: Observations in Quiescence, during Flares, and Implications for AU Mic b and c, *Astronomical Journal*, 164, 110, <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ac8107>
- S. Feister, K. Cassou, S. Dann, A. Döpp, P. Gauron, A. J. Gonsalves, A. Joglekar, V. Marshall, O. Neveu, H.-P. Schlenvoigt, M. J. V. Streeter, C. A. J. Palmer (2023). Control systems and data management for high-power laser facilities, *High Power Laser Science and Engineering*, 11, e56, <http://doi.org/10.1017/hpl.2023.49>
- K. Finch, D. Zhang, Y. She, A. Hernandez, G. Gamez (2021). Advances in Thomson scattering diagnostics of plasmas used for chemical analysis, *Spectrochimica Acta - Part B: Atomic Spectroscopy*, 176, 106045, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sab.2020.106045>
- Fusion Energy Sciences Advisory Committee (FESAC 2020). Powering the Future: Fusion and Plasmas. Final report. Available from: <https://science.osti.gov/fes/fesac/Reports>
- B. C. Foo, D. B. Schaeffer, & P. V. Heuer (2023). Recovering non-Maxwellian particle velocity distribution functions from collective Thomson-scattered spectra, *AIP Advances*, 13, 115328, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0169393>
- A. Fujisawa (2010), Observations of Turbulence and Structure in Magnetized Plasmas, *Plasma and Fusion Research*, 2010, 5, 46, <https://doi.org/10.1585/pfr.5.046>
- L. Gao; Y. Zhang; H. Ji; B. K. Russell; G. Pomraning; J. Griff-McMahon; S. Klein; C. Kuranz; M. Wei (2025). Record magnetic field generation by short-pulse laser-driven capacitor-coil targets, *Applied Physics Letters*, 127, 094101, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0279265>
- W. Gekelman, P. Pribyl, Z. Lucky, M. Drandell, D. Lineman, J. Maggs, S. Vincena, B. Van Compernelle, S. K. P. Tripathy, G. Morales, T. A. Carter, Y. Wang, T. DeHaas (2016). The upgraded Large Plasma Device, a machine for studying frontier basic plasma physics, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 87, 2, 025105, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4941079>
- M. González Garmendia (2025). Dinámica de electrones runaway en disrupciones Tokamak, <https://hdl.handle.net/10902/36778>
- T. Gruber, H.-P. Schlenvoigt, O. Knodel, K. Tippey, G. Jukeland (2023), Two-Step Approach in Metadata Management for Data Publications at Research Centers. *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure*, 1, <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.377>
- A. L. Haynes; C. E. Parnell (2007). A trilinear method for finding null points in a three-dimensional vector space. *Physics of Plasmas*, 14, 082107, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2756751>

- A. L. Haynes; C. E. Parnell (2010). A method for finding three-dimensional magnetic skeletons. *Physics of Plasmas*, 17, 092903, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3467499>
- P. V. Heuer, L. S. Leal, J. R. Davies, E. C. Hansen, D. H. Barnak, J. L. Peebles, F. García-Rubio, B. Pollock, J. Moody, A. Birkel, F. H. Séguin (2022). Diagnosing magnetic fields in cylindrical implosions with oblique proton radiography, *Physics of Plasmas*, 29, 072708, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0092652>
- P. V. Heuer; J. L. Peebles; J. Kunimune; H. G. Rinderknecht; J. R. Davies; V. Gopalaswamy; J. Frelier; M. Scott; J. Roberts; R. B. Brannon; H. McClow; R. Fairbanks; S. P. Regan; J. A. Frenje; M. Gatu Johnson; F. H. Séguin; A. J. Crilly; B. D. Appelbe; M. Farrell; J. Stutz (2025). Distortions in charged-particle images of laser direct-drive inertial confinement fusion implosions, *Physics of Plasmas*, 32, 042702, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0251899>
- N. C. Hurst; M. Abler; M. R. Brown; J. Juno; E. G. Kostadinova; N. A. Murphy; J. Olson; D. M. Orlov; D. B. Schaeffer; D. A. Schaffner; E. E. Scime; J. M. Tenbarge; S. C. Thakur (2025). MagNetUS: a magnetized plasma research ecosystem, *Journal of Plasma Physics*, 91, E32, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022377825000017>
- I. H. Hutchinson (2005). *Principles of Plasma Diagnostics*, 2nd edition, Cambridge University Press, ISBN 0521803896
- J. Jara-Almonte, N. A. Murphy, H. Ji (2021). Multi-fluid and kinetic models of partially ionized magnetic reconnection, *Physics of Plasmas*, 28, 042108, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0039860>
- H. Ji, J. Goodman (2023). Taylor–Couette flow for astrophysical purposes, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A*, 381, 20220119, <http://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2022.0119>
- E. Johnson, B. A. Maruca, M. McManus, K. G. Klein, E. R. Lichko, J. Verniero, K. W. Paulson, H. DeWeese, I. Dieguez, R. A. Qudsi, J. Kasper, M. Stevens, B. L. Alterman, L. B. Wilson, R. Livi, A. Rahmati, & D. Larson (2023). Anterograde Collisional Analysis of Solar Wind Ions, *Astrophysical Journal*, 950, 51, <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/accc32>
- E. Johnson, B. A. Maruca, M. McManus, M. Stevens, K. G. Klein, & P. Mostafavi (2024). Application of collisional analysis to the differential velocity of solar wind ions, *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences*, 10, 1284913, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2023.1284913>
- E. Johnson (2024). Coulomb Collisional Analysis of Solar Wind Ions, Ph.D. thesis, University of Delaware
- S. Jubin, A. T. Powis, W. Villafana, D. Sydorenko, S. Rauf, A. V. Khrabrov, S. Sarwar, I. D. Kaganovich (2024). Numerical thermalization in 2D PIC simulations: Practical estimates for low-temperature plasma simulations, *Physics of Plasmas*, 31, 023902, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0180421>
- E. Krämer, M. Hamrin, H. Gunell, T. Karlsson, K. Steinvall, O. Goncharov, M. André (2023). Waves in Magnetosheath Jets—Classification and the Search for Generation Mechanisms Using MMS Burst Mode Data, *Journal of Geophysical Research (Space Physics)*, 128, e2023JA031621, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JA031621>
- Kennedy, M.; Salmonson, J. (2023). Fusion Ignition Breakthrough and Python. Talk Python To Me, podcast #403, <https://talkpython.fm/episodes/show/403/fusion-ignition-breakthrough-and-python>
- Kinoshita, G.; Sanchez-Cano, B.; Miyoshi, Y. (2025). Spatio-Temporal Evolution of the March 2022 ICME Revealed by Multi-Point Observations of Forbush Decreases, arXiv: 2510.12296, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2510.12296>
- H. J. Kunze (2009). Introduction to plasma spectroscopy (Vol. 56). Springer Science & Business Media.

LaserNetUS (2023). Report on the 2023 LaserNetUS Data & Diagnostics Workshop, https://lasernetus.org/uploads/LaserNetUS-DDW-2023-Final-Report_1.pdf

J. Lee (2025). Development of a Collective Thomson Scattering Diagnostic on SNU X-pinch Device, Master's Thesis of Nuclear Engineering, Seoul National University, <https://hdl.handle.net/10371/220645>

D. Leonard (2018). PLEP-0006 — A New General-Purpose Plasma Object. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1460977>

MagNetUS (2022). MagNetUS Bylaws, ratified by membership on 2025 August 5, <https://sites.google.com/view/frontier-science-magnetus/magnetus-bylaws>

B. A. Maruca, J. A. Agudelo Rueda, R. Bandyopadhyay, F. B. Bianco, A. Chasapis, R. Chhiber, H. DeWeese, W. H. Matthaeus, D. M. Miles, R. A. Qudsi, M. J. Richardson, S. Servidio, M. A. Shay, D. Sundkvist, D. Verscharen, S. K. Vines, J. H. Westlake, & R. T. Wicks (2021). MagneToRE: Mapping the 3-D Magnetic Structure of the Solar Wind Using a Large Constellation of Nanosatellites, *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Science*, 8, 665885, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2021.665885>

R. McWilliams and D. Edrich (2003). Laser-induced fluorescence diagnosis of plasma processing sources, *Thin Solid Films*, Volume 435, Issues 1–2, ISSN 0040-6090, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6090\(03\)00358-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6090(03)00358-4).

A. Murphy & J. Morelli (2023). Design of an asymmetrically biased triple Langmuir probe and accompanying diagnostics tool, *Canadian Journal of Undergraduate Research*, 8, 1, <https://ojs.library.ubc.ca/index.php/cjur/article/view/198594>

L. Murphy, Causes of changing parallel plasma velocity in the Large Plasma Device (2024). Undergraduate Honors Theses, William & Mary, <https://scholarworks.wm.edu/honorstheses/2239>

N. A. Murphy, J. C. Raymond, K. E. Korreck (2011). Plasma Heating During a Coronal Mass Ejection Observed By the Solar and Heliospheric Observatory, *Astrophysical Journal*, 735, 17, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/735/1/17>

Murphy, N. A.; Stańczak, D.; Leonard, A. J.; Parashar, T.; Kozłowski, P. M.; Alterman, B. L.; Roberts, D. A.; Christe, S. D.; Connors, M.; Bobra, M.; Mason, J. P.; Barnes, W.; McGranaghan, R. M.; Bhatt, A.; Erikson, P. J.; Lind, F. D.; Volz, R.; Swoboda, J.; Hatzigeorgiu, N.; Inglis, A.; deOliveira-Lopes, F. N.; Ireland, J.; Coxon, J. C.; Murray, S. A.; Yates, J. N.; Cheung, M. C. M.; Klenzing, J.; Stansby, D.; He, H.; Huang, Y.-M.; Dong, C.; Winter, H.; Buitrago-Casas, J.-C.; Kaur, M.; Smith, S.; Dudson, B.; Seaton, D. B.; Comisso, L.; Halford, A. J.; Barnak, D. H.; Weigel, R. S.; Tavant, A.; Vandegriff, J. D.; de Val-Borro, M.; Savcheva, A. (2019a). Building an open source software ecosystem for cross-disciplinary plasma research and education. Zenodo, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2578277>

Murphy, N. A.; Alterman, B. L.; Stansby, D.; Dominguez, A.; Stańczak, D. (2019b). Enabling scientific reproducibility in plasma research. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3265454>

Murphy, N. A. (2022a). Open source software and data for fusion energy sciences. Joint ICTP-IAEA Advanced School/Workshop on Computational Nuclear Science and Engineering. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6585147>

Murphy, N. A. (2023a). Writing Clean Scientific Software. IDEAS-ECP webinar. Video at: <https://youtu.be/toO0G5gZMs0?si=hp9qpR7wDoL8QnRG>

Murphy, N. A. (2023b). Writing Clean Scientific Software, version 4, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185113>

Murphy, Nicholas A. (2023c). Making plasma science open. Adapted from slides presented at the Computational Physics School for Fusion Research (CPS-FR) in 2023. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8404466>

National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM 2021). Plasma Science: Enabling Technology, Sustainability, Security, and Exploration. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/25802>

C. Niemann, W. Gekelman, C.G. Constantin, E.T. Everson, D.B. Schaeffer, A.S. Bondarenko, S.E. Clark, D. Winske, S. Vincena, B. Van Compernelle, P. Pribyl (2014). Observation of collisionless shocks in a large current-free laboratory plasma. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 41, 21, 7413, <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014GL061820>

J. J. Pilgram, C. G. Constantin, H. Zhang, P. Tzeferacos, T. G. Bachmann, L. Rovige, P. V. Heuer, M. B. P. Adams, S. Ghazaryan, M. Kaloyan, R. S. Dorst, M. J.-E. Manuel, & C. Niemann (2024). Two-dimensional Thomson scattering measurements of misaligned electron density and temperature gradients and associated Biermann battery produced fields, *Physics of Plasmas*, 31, 042113, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0201112>

PlasmaPy Community, Murphy N. A., Everson E, Stańczak-Marikin D, Heuer P, Kozłowski P, Johnson E, Malhotra R, Schaffner D, Vincena S, Abler M, Addison J, Ahamed A, Alarcon P, Antognetti B, Arran C, Bagherianlemraski H, Beckers J, Bedmutha M, Bedoya-Lopez C, Bergeron J, Bessi L, Britten R, Brown S, Bryant K, Carroll S, Cartagena-Sanchez C, Chambers S, Chattopadhyay A, Choubey A, Choudhary S, Clauss C, Colom S, Davies C, Deal J, Decristoforo G, Diaz Riega D, Dover F, Drozdov D, Du T, Einhorn L, Ervin T, Fan T, Farid S, Fischer M, Foo B, Fütterer H, Gangadharan R, Gerow S, Gonzalez J, Goodall B, Gorelli M, Gordon-McKeon S, Goudeau G, Guidoni S, Guimiot J, Haggerty C, Hansen R, Haque M, Hillairet J, Hoang C, How P, Huang Y, Humphrey N, Isupova M, Jeandet A, Jones E, Kastek M, Kent J, Klima D, Köhn-Seemann A, Kulshrestha S, Kumar S, Kuszaj P, Langendorf S, Lanteri A, Lee T, Leonard D, Lequette N, Lim P, Magarde A, Martinelli J, Masood M, McHardy I, Modi D, Montes K, Mumford S, Munn J, Murphy L, Nie S, Ortiz C, Panda S, Pannala M, Parashar T, Patel N, Pavon F, Pérez R, Pitzer P, Polak J, Qudsi R, Raj R, Rajashekar V, Rao A, Reep J, Richardson S, Roberts J, Rodriguez S, Rojas Zelaya R, Salcido A, Savcheva A, Schneck C, Shen C, Sheng A, Sherpa D, Silvestri L, Simon T, Singh A, Singh A, Sipócz B, Skinner C, Skrzypczak T, Smirnov N, Smith J, Sobeske S, Spedicato M, Stansby D, Stinson T, Sugiharto S, Švancarová M, Tavant A, Tranquilino V, Ulrich T, Valle M, Varnish T, Vo T, Wu T, Xu S, Yip C, & Zhang C (2024). PlasmaPy. Python package, v2024.10.0. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14010450>

C. Pliatskas Stylianidis (2019). Fast ion detection in collective Thomson scattering spectra with neural networks, Master's thesis, Eindhoven University of Technology

M. Pokornik, D. P. Higginson, G. Swadling, D. Larson, K. Moczulski, B. Pollock, E. Tubman, P. Tzeferacos, H. S. Park, F. Beg, A. Arefiev, M. Manuel (2024). A deep learning approach to fast analysis of collective Thomson scattering spectra, *Physics of Plasmas*, 31, 072115, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0201148>

S. Polson, R. Ringuette, L. Rastaetter, E. Grimes, J. Niehof, N. A. Murphy, Y. Zheng (2023). Making an executable paper with the Python in Heliophysics Community to foster open science and improve reproducibility, *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences*, 9, 977781, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2022.977781>

R. A. Qudsi (2021). On the interplay between microkinetics and turbulence in space plasmas, Ph.D. thesis, University of Delaware

- J. C. Raymond, M. Asgari-Targhi, M. L. Wilson, Y. J. Rivera, S. T. Lepri, C. Shen (2022). Dropouts of Fully Stripped Ions in the Solar Wind: A Diagnostic for Wave Heating versus Reconnection, *Astrophysical Journal*, 936, 175, <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac8976>
- G. Rigon, C. Stoeckl, T. M. Johnson, J. Katz, J. Peebles, C. K. Li (2024). Development of a platform for experimental and computational studies of magnetic and radiative effects on astrophysically relevant jets at OMEGA, *Physics of Plasmas*, 31, 042902, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0196254>
- Schaeffer, D. B.; Cruz, F. D.; Dorst, R. S.; Cruz, F.; Heuer, P. V.; Constantin, C. G.; Pribyl, P.; Nimeann, C.; Silva, L. O.; Bhattacharjee, A. (2022). Laser-driven, ion-scale magnetospheres in laboratory plasmas. I. Experimental platform and first results. *Physics of Plasmas*, 29, 04290, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0084353>
- D. B. Schaeffer, A. F. A. Bott, M. Borghesi, K. A. Flippo, W. Fox, J. Fuchs, C. Li, F. H. Séguin, H.-S. Park, P. Tzeferacos, & L. Willingale (2023). Proton imaging of high-energy-density laboratory plasmas, *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 95, 045007, <https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.95.045007>
- D. A. Schaffner, T. A. Carter, G. D. Rossi, D. S. Guice, J. E. Maggs, S. Vincena, B. Friedman (2012). Modification of Turbulent Transport with Continuous Variation of Flow Shear in the Large Plasma Device, *Physical Review Letters*, 109, 13, 135002, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.109.135002>
- J. W. Schroeder, G. G. Howes, C. A. Kletzing, F. Skiff, T. A. Carter, S. Vincena, S. Dorfman (2021). Laboratory measurements of the physics of auroral electron acceleration by Alfvén waves, *Nature communications*, 12, 1, 3103, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-23377-5>
- R. A. Simpson, D. A. Mariscal, J. Kim, N. Lemos, E. S. Grace, K. K. Swanson, G. G. Scott, B. Z. Djordjevic, T. Ma (2023). Investigation of boosted proton energies through proton radiography of target normal sheath acceleration fields in the multi-ps regime, *Physics of Plasmas*, 30, 103103, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0157214>
- SunPy Community, W. T. Barnes, S. Christe, N. Freij, L. A. Hayes, D. Stansby, J. Ireland, S. J. Mumford, D. F. Ryan, A. Y. Shih (2023). The SunPy Project: An interoperable ecosystem for solar data analysis, *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences*, 10, 1076726, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2023.1076726>
- T. Tajima (2004), *Computational Plasma Physics: With Applications To Fusion And Astrophysics*, CRC Press, ISBN 0813342112
- V. Valenzuela-Villaseca, S. Totorica, J. Griff-McMahon, L.-J. Chen, S. Malko, P. V. Heuer, P. Pongkitiwanchakul, W. Fox, D. B. Schaeffer (2025). Anomalous electron heating in laboratory magnetized quasi-perpendicular collisionless shocks, [arXiv:2509.12164](https://arxiv.org/abs/2509.12164), <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2509.12164>
- Verscharen, D.; Chandran, B. D. G. (2018). NHDS: The New Hampshire Dispersion Relation Solver. *Research Notes of the AAS*, 2, 13, <https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/aabfe3>
- S. Vincena, S. K. P. Tripathi, W. Gekelman, P. Pribyl (2024). Three-wave coupling observed between a shear Alfvén wave and a kink-unstable magnetic flux rope, *Physics of Plasmas*, 31, 092302, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0217895>
- Wilkinson, M. D.; Dumontier, M.; Aalbersberg, I. J.; Appleton, G.; Axton, M.; Baak, A.; Blomberg, N.; Boiten, J.-W.; da Silva Santos, L. B.; Bourne, P. E.; Bouwman, J.; Brookes, A. J.; Clark, T.; Crosas, M.; Dillo, I.; Dumon, O.; Edmunds, S.; Evelo, C. T.; Finkers, R.; Gonzalez-Beltran, A.; Gray, A. J. G.; Groth, P.; Goble, C.; Grethe, J. S.; Heringa, J.; 'T Hoen, P. A. C.; Hooft, R.; Kuhn, T.; Kok, R.; Kok, J.; Lusher, S. J.; Martone, M. E.; Mons, A.; Packer, A. L.; Persson, B.; Rocca-Serra, P.; Roos, M.; van Schaik, R.; Sansone, S.-A.; Schultes, E.; Sengstag, T.; Slater, T.; Strawn, G.; Swertz, M. A.; Thompson, M.; van der Lei, J.; van Mulligen, E.; Velterop, J.; Waagmeester, A.; Wittenburg, P.;

- Wolstencroft, K.; Zhao, J.; Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018, <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Wilson, G.; Aruliah, D. A.; Brown, C. T.; Chue Hong, N. P.; Davis, M.; Guy, R.; Haddock, S.; Huff, K. D.; Mitchell, I.; Plumbly, M.; Waugh, B.; White, E.; Wilson, P. (2014). Best Practices for Scientific Computing. *PLoS Biology*, 12, 1, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001745>
- Wilson, M. L.; Raymond, J. C.; Lepri, S. T.; Lionello, R.; Murphy, N. A.; Reeves, K. K.; Shen, C. (2022). Constraining the CME Core Heating and Energy Budget with SOHO/UVCS. *Astrophysical Journal*, 927, 27, <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac4d35>
- Wójcik, D.; Macek, W. M. (2025). Searching for universality of turbulence in the Earth's magnetosphere. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 130, e2025JA034020. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2025JA034020>
- Xie, H. (2014). PDRF: A general dispersion relation solver for magnetized multi-fluid plasma. *Computer Physics Communications*, 185, 670, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2013.10.012>
- Xie Huasheng (谢华生); Xiao Yong (肖湧). (2014). PDRK: A General Kinetic Dispersion Relation Solver for Magnetized Plasma. *Plasma Science and Technology*, 18, 97, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1009-0630/18/2/01>
- M. Yamada; R. Kulsrud; H. Ji (2010). Magnetic reconnection, *Reviews of modern physics*, 82, 1, pp.603-664, <https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.82.603>
- H. Zhang; J. J. Pilgram; C. G. Constantin; L. Rovige; P. V. Heuer; S. Ghazaryan; M. Kaloyan; R. S. Dorst; D. B. Schaeffer; C. Niemann (2023). Two-Dimensional Thomson Scattering in Laser-Produced Plasmas, *Instruments*, 7, 3, <https://doi.org/10.3390/instruments7030025>
- Y. Zhang; L. Gao; H. Ji; B. K. Russell; G. Pomraning; J. Griff-McMahon, S. Klein; C. Kuranz; M. Wei (2025). Diagnosing electric and magnetic fields in laser-driven coil targets, *Plasma Physics and Controlled Fusion*, 67, 085039, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6587/adfd12>